

NFDI4Objects

Research Data Infrastructure
for the Material Remains of
Human History

KD111t
Kompetenzzentrum
Denkmalwissenschaften
und -technologien

GOETHE
UNIVERSITÄT
FRANKFURT AM MAIN

Workshop III: Linked Open Data am Beispiel von RDF-Daten, Wikidata und Wikibase

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Dr. Karsten Tolle (Goethe-Universität Frankfurt)

Dr. Tobias-Arera Rütenik (Universität Bamberg)

NFDI4Objects Community Meeting 2024 | Mainz | 25.09.2024

Wer sind wir?

NFDI4Objects

Community Cluster
Semantic Modelling
& Linked Open Data

LEIZA Forschung Museen

Start > Über uns > Team > Florian Thiery, M.Sc.

Florian Thiery, M.Sc.

Research Software Engineer (NFDI4Objects)

Forschungsprofil

- Research Software Engineering
- Semantische Modellierung (semantic modelling)
- Linked Open Data / Wikidata
- Vagheiten und Unsicherheiten (Fuzziness and Wobbliness)
- Relative Chronologie

WERDEGANG

Akademischer Werdegang

- 2013: Master-Thesis, Semantic Web und Linked Data: Generierung von Interoperabilität in archäologischen Fachdaten am Beispiel römischer Topferstempel, Betreuer: Prof. Dr. phil. Kai-Christian Bruhn, Partner: i3mainz and RGZM, Note: 1.0 (sehr gut)
- 2011-2013: Studium der Geoinformatik und Vermessung an der Fachhochschule Mainz, Abschluss: Master of Science, Note 1.5 (sehr gut)
- 2011: Bachelor-Thesis: Eignung aktueller Industriekameras für modulare Digitalkameratachymeter, Betreuer: Prof. Dr.-Ing. Martin Schlüter, Partner: i3mainz, Note: 1.7 (gut)
- 2007-2011: Studium der Geoinformatik und Vermessung an der Fachhochschule Mainz, Abschluss: Bachelor of Science, Note: 2.3 (gut)

KONTAKT

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ORCID

Tellen

Link kopieren

Artikel drucken

GOETHE UNIVERSITÄT FRANKFURT AM MAIN Big Data Lab

HOME PEOPLE PROJECTS TRUSTWORTHY AI LAB COMPLETED THESES GITHUB

Dr. Karsten Tolle

Dr. Karsten Tolle

Senior Researcher, Big Data Lab Director,
korrespondierendes Mitglied des Deutschen Archäologischen Instituts

With Z-Inspection® we want to help to establish what we call a Mindful Use of AI (#MUAI). Certified Z-Inspection® Teaching Expert, also have a look at our: [Trustworthy AI lab](#)

My research interests are in Digital Humanities and Linked Open Data (LOD):

- Machine Learning (NLP, Deep Learning / Image Recognition)
- Trustworthy AI
- Data Quality
- Modelling uncertainty
- Linking LOD
- Big Data benchmarking / Performance optimizations

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Universität Bamberg

Institut für Archäologische Wissenschaften, Denkmalwissenschaften und Kunstgeschichte

Bauforschung und Baugeschichte

Kontrast Deutsch

Institut für Archäologische Wissenschaften, Denkmalwissenschaften und Kunstgeschichte

> Fakultäten > Geistes- und Kulturwissenschaften > Institute > Institut für Archäologische Wissenschaften, Denkmalwissenschaften und Kunstgeschichte > Denkmalwissenschaften > Bauforschung und Baugeschichte > Team > **Dr.-Ing. Tobias Arera-Rütenik**

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News

Team

- Prof. Dr.-Ing Stefan Breittling
- Jürgen Giese M.A.
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- Gesa Fellner M.A.
- Leonhard Salzer M.A.

Linked Data in NFDI4Objects

Warum das Ganze?

The road into the FAIR Linked Open Data Cloud and back

Samian Research relational database

Linked Open Data based on CIDOC CRM

publication via archaeology.link

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryhelper Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen: Wikidata -> ?item ?geo [SPARQL Endpoint] Quick Add RDF Resource

Filter Concept Results:

GeoConcepts (500) FeatureCollections GeometryC4

Valid Query

```

1 PREFIX wd: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/>
2 PREFIX wdt: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/direct/>
3 PREFIX wikibase: <http://wikiba.se/ontology#>
4 PREFIX p: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/>
5 PREFIX ps: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/statement/>
6 PREFIX pq: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/qualifier/>
7 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
8 PREFIX bd: <http://www.bigdata.com/rdf#>
9
10 #defaultView:Map{"hide":["?geo"]}
11 # Samian Ware Productioncentres
12 SELECT ?item ?samian ?itemLabel ?geo ?layerLabel ?layer WHERE {
13   ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q102202026;
14   wdt:P361 wd:Q90412636;
15   wdt:P625 ?geo;
16   wdt:P2888 ?samian;
17   wdt:P706 ?layer.
18   ?layer wdt:P31 wd:Q102201947.
19   SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
20 }

```

Gespeicherte Queries: ChristSch Query laden Queryname: Query speichern

Layer hinzufügen

Language for query results: English (en)

via <https://w.wiki/BA3A>

SPARQL Unicorn

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0. Data via Wikidata, CCO and Samian Research, m-DPPL

LOD in Action!

... am Beispiel nomisma.org

Münzen als Beispiel (weil so schön einfach:-)

Antike Münzen:

... wo gefunden?

... Gemeinsamkeiten?

... wo sind die gef. Exemplare?

Denar von Kaiser Nero:

Wo finde ich Denari von Nero?

Nomisma.org

Nomisma.org is an international, collaborative project to provide stable digital representations of numismatic concepts according to the principles of [Linked Open Data](#) (LOD). These take the form of HTTP URIs that also provide access to reusable information about those concepts, along with links to other resources. The Nomisma.org community maintains a formalized [RDF Ontology](#) and a data model for encoding concepts, coins, typologies, hoards, and other types of numismatic objects as LOD.

Since 2010, the nomisma.org project has been hosted and financially supported by the American Numismatic Society in New York. It was founded by Andrew Meadows, then deputy director of the Society, and Sebastian Heath, its data scientist. The current Principal Developer of the Nomisma project is Ethan Gruber, Director of Data Science at the ANS.

The information made available by Nomisma.org has been provided by a wide community of scholars and institutions. All concepts published by Nomisma.org domain are openly accessible with a CC-BY license. See the [Datasets](#) page for further license statements

www.nomisma.org

How to Contribute Data

In the spring of 2013, we took a new approach in establishing links from RIC types in OC in OCRE and similar coin type projects based on the Numishare platform that relies on

The first basic prerequisite for participation is that each object you wish to contribute be the Pelagios Network: an RDF data dump (which also much be accessible by URL) and

VOID RDF

This snippet of RDF is intended to describe the contents of a dataset with general metad

```

<rdf:RDF xmlns:rdf="http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#"
  xmlns:dcterms="http://purl.org/dc/terms/"
  xmlns:void="http://rdfs.org/ns/void#"
  <void:Dataset rdf:about="http://coins.lib.virginia.edu/"
    <dcterms:title>The Fralin | UVA Art Museum Numismatic Collectio
    <dcterms:description>The Fralin Museum of Art at the University
      collection contains about 600 coins of mainly Greco-Roman o
    <dcterms:publisher>University of Virginia Library</dcterms:publ
    <dcterms:license rdf:resource="http://opendatacommons.org/licen
    <void:uriSpace>http://coins.lib.virginia.edu/id/</void:uriSpace
    <void:dataDump rdf:resource="http://coins.lib.virginia.edu/nomi
  </void:Dataset>
</rdf:RDF>
    
```

The void:Dataset should include the URI for your project, and this URI should be linked fr The title and description must be textual strings, but the publisher and license may be U dcterms:license link.

Nomisma-compliant RDF export Models

The data dump model should conform to the standards established by Nomisma.org, inc types of materials are represented by minor variations of the Nomisma ontology.

Physical Coins

```

<rdf:RDF xmlns:dcterms="http://purl.org/dc/terms/"
  xmlns:void="http://rdfs.org/ns/void#"
  xmlns:nmo="http://nomisma.org/ontology#"
  xmlns:rdf="http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#"
  xmlns:foaf="http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/"
    
```

Physical Coins

```

<rdf:RDF xmlns:dcterms="http://purl.org/dc/terms/"
  xmlns:void="http://rdfs.org/ns/void#"
  xmlns:nmo="http://nomisma.org/ontology#"
  xmlns:rdf="http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#"
  xmlns:foaf="http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/"
  xmlns:xsd="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#">
  <nmo:NumismaticObject rdf:about="http://coins.lib.virginia.edu/id/1991.17.140">
    <dcterms:title>Antoninianus of Gallienus, Rome, 254-255. 1991.17.140.</dcterms:title>
    <dcterms:identifier>1991.17.140</dcterms:identifier>
    <nmo:hasCollection rdf:resource="http://nomisma.org/id/uva"/>
    <nmo:hasTypeSeriesItem rdf:resource="http://numismatics.org/ocre/id/ric.5.gall(1).143fA"/>
    <dcterms:replaces rdf:resource="http://coins.lib.virginia.edu/display-uva?id=n1991_17_140"/>
    <nmo:hasAxis rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer">6</nmo:hasAxis>
    <nmo:hasDiameter rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#decimal">22</nmo:hasDiameter>
    <nmo:hasWeight rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#decimal">2.86</nmo:hasWeight>
    <dcterms:isPartOf rdf:resource="http://nomisma.org/id/olivers_orchard_hoards"/>
    <nmo:hasObverse rdf:resource="http://coins.lib.virginia.edu/id/1991.17.140#obverse"/>
    <nmo:hasReverse rdf:resource="http://coins.lib.virginia.edu/id/1991.17.140#reverse"/>
    <void:inDataset rdf:resource="http://coins.lib.virginia.edu"/>
  </nmo:NumismaticObject>
  <rdf:Description rdf:about="http://coins.lib.virginia.edu/id/1991.17.140#obverse">
    <foaf:depiction rdf:resource="http://coins.lib.virginia.edu/images/coins/screen/n1991_17_140_obv.jpg"/>
    <foaf:thumbnail rdf:resource="http://coins.lib.virginia.edu/images/coins/thumb/n1991_17_140_obv.jpg"/>
  </rdf:Description>
  <rdf:Description rdf:about="http://coins.lib.virginia.edu/id/1991.17.140#reverse">
    <foaf:depiction rdf:resource="http://coins.lib.virginia.edu/images/coins/screen/n1991_17_140_rev.jpg"/>
    <foaf:thumbnail rdf:resource="http://coins.lib.virginia.edu/images/coins/thumb/n1991_17_140_rev.jpg"/>
  </rdf:Description>
</rdf:RDF>
    
```

Count	Data Dump
97603	↓ ↓ ↓ ↓ ↓
32956	↓ ↓ ↓
40267	↓ ↓ ↓
55	↓
26879	↓ ↓

α μνημό, τιμὰς, μυσία, ἀν

Physical Coins

```
<rdf:RDF xmlns:dcterms="http://purl.org/dc/terms/"  
  xmlns:void="http://rdfs.org/ns/void#"  
  xmlns:nmo="http://nomisma.org/ontology#"  
  xmlns:foaf="http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/"  
  xmlns:xsd="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#">
```


Namespaces:
dcterms: http://purl.org/dc/terms/
void: http://rdfs.org/ns/void#
nmo: http://nomisma.org/ontology#
rdf: http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#
foaf: http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/
xsd: http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#

SPARQL Endpoint

For examples, see [SPARQL Examples](#). A basic tutorial on SPARQL is available from [Apache Jena](#).

```
PREFIX crm: <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/>
PREFIX dcterms: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
PREFIX dcmitype: <http://purl.org/dc/dcmitype/>
PREFIX foaf: <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/>
PREFIX geo: <http://www.w3.org/2003/01/geo/wgs84_pos#>
PREFIX nm: <http://nomisma.org/id/>
PREFIX nmo: <http://nomisma.org/ontology#>
PREFIX org: <http://www.w3.org/ns/org#>
PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX skos: <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
```

```
SELECT * WHERE {
  ?s ?p ?o
} LIMIT 100
```

Additional prefixes

Output

▾

Support this resource by joining the American Numismatic Society as a member

Typ: Head of Augustus, bare, right
Porträt: Augustus

Augustus ca. 25-23 v. Chr.
Collection Münzkabinett Berlin
Identifier 18207657
Axis 3
Diameter (in mm) 18
Weight (in g) 3.46

Augustus ca. 25-23 v. Chr.
Collection Münzkabinett Berlin
Identifier 18207656
Axis 4
Diameter (in mm) 19
Weight (in g) 3.50

zstätte Hoard Fundste

3 Silver Denarius of Augustus, Emerita, 25 B
Sammlung American Num
Stellung 9
Durchmesser 19.5
Gewicht 3.85

British Museum: 1843,1024.257
Collection British Museum
Axis 3
Weight (in g) 3.7

Augustus und P. Carisius 25 bis 23 v. Chr.
Collection Münzsammlung des Seminars für Alte Geschichte der Albert-Ludwigs-Universität
Identifier ID4655
Axis 11
Diameter (in mm) 18
Weight (in g) 3.87

[Monnaie. Denarius, Auguste, Emerita]
Sammlung Bibliothèque m
Inventarnummer IMP-4726
Gewicht 3.76

Au Stellung 9
Dvnastie: Julisch-Claudische Dvnastie

... und viele andere ...

und viele andere ...

ARCH

A typology of Ancient Greek Coinage

The ARCH project uses Linked Open Data technology and the standards of the [nomisma.org](#) project to establish an overarching portal for the study heritage of the ancient world – the Greek *oikoumene*. It aims to present a high-level overview of all the coin types traditionally subsumed within the century BC. These are made available partly through a new typology (IRIS) created as part of the ARCH project based on existing bibliography, at specific regions or types of coinage. The constituent parts can be found at:

- [IRIS](#)
- [Moneda Iberica \(MIB\)](#)
- [Hellenistic Royal Coinage](#)
- [Corpus Nummorum Online](#)

Geographically, the project thus encompasses the ancient Mediterranean world and all of its cultures (with the exception of Rome and its province eastern limits of the empire of Alexander the Great). The following regions and coinages are not included and may be consulted elsewhere:

- [Parthia: parthia.com](#)
- [Bactria and the Indo-Greeks: The OXUS-INDUS Project](#)
- [Iron-Age Britain: Iron Age Coins in Britain](#)

<https://greekcoinage.org/arch/>

Welcome to Change

CHANGE is an interdisciplinary project to research the monetary history of ancient Anatolia from the beginning of coinage in the 7th century to the absorption of the region by Rome circa 30 BC. In partnership with the [British Museum](#) and the [Münzkabinett](#) of the [Staatliche Museen zu Berlin](#), researchers based at the Centre for the Study of Ancient Documents are gathering the epigraphic and numismatic evidence for the monetary history of Anatolia with a view to creating new research tools and a new history of monetary behaviour of the region where coinage was born.

The **CHANGE** project is gathering, for the first time, the evidence for the development of the monetary economy of ancient Anatolia and, using new digital technology, it is organising this evidence to answer major questions concerning the economic history of this region over the longue durée. A new monetary history of Asia Minor will result, encompassing such broad themes as the origins of coinage, the economies of cities, dynasts and empires and the emergence of fiduciarity.

Findspots

Mints

Inscriptions

<https://change.web.ox.ac.uk/home>

Komplexe Objekte im semantischen Graph

Theoretische Überlegungen am Beispiel historischer Bauwerke

Schloss Hofstetten

- Ort: Hitzhofen
- Kreis: Landkreis Eichstätt
- BLfD-ID: D-1-7133-0166
- WGS84: 48.87293, 11.32797
- Bautyp: Wasserburg, Dreiflügelanlage
- Lagetyp: Niederungslage
- Nutzungstyp: Ministerialsitz, Jagschloss, landesherrliches Schloss, Adelsburg
- Erhaltung: weitgehend erhalten
- Grundriss: rechteckig, trapezförmig

Das Bauwerk als Einzelobjekt ...

Eckerker

Hocheingang

Eckquaderung
Buckelquader

Kapellenraum

Bergfried

Rechteckfenster

Wappenschild

Wohnbau

Eckturm
Schalenturm

Bruchstein-
mauerwerk

Ringmauer

Eckturm
Schalenturm

... ist tatsächlich eine strukturierte Sammlung zahlloser Teilobjekte.

Kurze Einführung in Semantische Graphen

Für diejenigen, die damit noch nicht sattelfest vertraut sind.

Aber auch für alle anderen, die es jetzt hier eben nochmal hören dürfen und sich hoffentlich nicht langweilen.

D. h.: "hat reales Beispiel" ist die inverse Eigenschaft von "ist ein".

instance | Instanz | Individuum | Ausprägung einer Klasse

Ist eine einmalige, "einzigartige" Entität. Bezüglich gebauter Objekte betrifft dies z. B. ein konkretes / individuelles Gebäude an einem spezifischen Ort, wie der "Mainzer Dom"..

class | Kategorie | verallgemeinerbares Konzept

Abstrakte "Sammlung" von Entitäten, die sich in Eigenschaften gleichen (jedoch nicht zu verwechseln mit einem Set konkreter Instanzen). Bezüglich gebauter Objekte betrifft dies zum Beispiel den allgemeinen Bautyp "Dom", von dem z.B. der "Mainzer Dom" eine konkrete Instanz bildet.

Klassen können im Sinne von *subclasses* und *metaclasses* miteinander in Beziehung stehen. In einer ordentlichen formalen Ontologie werden zwischen Sub- und Metaklassen sowie zwischen Klassen und Instanzen von Klassen mögliche, zu verwendende Beziehungen beschränkt und definiert.

Vererbung von Eigenschaften

Die **Instanz** (*instance*) einer Klasse besitzt stets alle in der zugewiesenen Klasse definierten Eigenschaften.

Die **subclass** einer *metaclass* besitzt genauso alle in der zugewiesenen Metaklasse definierten Eigenschaften. Sie stellt eine Spezialisierung der Metaklasse dar und weist demnach zusätzliche kategorisierende Eigenschaften auf.

in Wikidata:

P31 (*is instance of* | *ist ein/e*)

P279 (*subclass of* | *Unterklasse von*)

in RDF:

rdf:type (Erzeugung von Instanzen)

rdf:subClassOf (Unterklassen)

Vererbung von Eigenschaften

property | Eigenschaft | Prädikat im Graphen

Auch *properties* (Eigenschaften) lassen sich durch *sub-properties* spezifizieren oder in umgekehrter Richtung verallgemeinern.

Am Rande sei noch angemerkt: Bedingungen / Einschränkungen / Festlegungen des Datenmodells betreffen u. U. auch den **Datentyp** des Zielobjekts, auf das die Eigenschaft referenziert.

Assertion Box (ABox)

Die **ABox** enthält das Wissen über konkrete Instanzen, d.h. Fakten über die Individuen und deren Eigenschaften sowie ihre Beziehungen untereinander.

Terminology Box (TBox)

Die **TBox** enthält das Wissen über die Konzepte, also das terminologische Wissen. Hier wird definiert, welche Klassen von Objekten es gibt und welche Eigenschaften sie haben.

KNOWLEDGE-GRAPH

Äpfel und Birnen vergleichen

<https://www.wikidata.org>

Offene Webanwendung mit
eigenem Datenmodell;

Keine stringente Trennung
zwischen Klassen und
Instanzen (implizit);

12.118 Properties; 247.776
Klassen;

Projekt der Wikimedia
Deutschland;

verwendet SPARQL zur
Abfrage.

<https://cidoc-crm.org>

Rein theoretische
Klassenontologie;

Klassen und Eigenschaften
sowie logische Regeln sind
definiert;

198 Eigenschaften;
99 Klassen;

Durch AG des ICOM definiert;

hat mit Erlangen-CRM eine
OWL-DL Implementierung
erfahren.

<https://www.w3.org/RDF/>
<https://www.w3.org/OWL/>

RDF: Framework/Syntax zur
Beschreibung von Ressourcen im
Semantic Web;

OWL: darauf aufbauende
Beschreibungslogik zur Definition
von Klassen, Eigenschaften und
deren Beziehungen;

Durch AG's des W3C definiert;

Definition von SPARQL zur Abfrage

Anwendung

Q24254990
Schloss Hofstetten

P31
ist ein/e

Q1424449
Jagdschloss

Schloss Hofstetten (Q24254990)

Bauwerk in Deutschland bearbeiten

Sprache

Sprache	Bezeichnung	Beschreibung	Auch bekannt als
Deutsch	Schloss Hofstetten	Bauwerk in Deutschland	
Englisch	Keine Bezeichnung vorhanden	Keine Beschreibung vorhanden	
Spanisch	Keine Bezeichnung vorhanden	Keine Beschreibung vorhanden	
Portugiesisch	Keine Bezeichnung vorhanden	Keine Beschreibung vorhanden	

Alle eingegebenen Sprachen

Aussagen

ist ein(e)

- Bauwerk bearbeiten
+ Fundstelle hinzufügen
- Jagdschloss bearbeiten
+ Fundstelle hinzufügen

Staat

- Deutschland bearbeiten
+ Fundstelle hinzufügen

liegt in der Verwaltungseinheit

- Hitzhofen bearbeiten
+ Fundstelle hinzufügen

geographische Koordinaten

48°52'22.490"N, 11°19'40.480"E

steht in der Denkmalliste

- Liste der Baudenkmäler in Hitzhofen bearbeiten
+ Fundstelle hinzufügen

Schutzkategorie

- Baudenkmal in Bayern bearbeiten
+ Fundstelle hinzufügen

Adresse

- Schloßstraße 28 (Deutsch) bearbeiten
+ Fundstelle hinzufügen

Identifikatoren

- Alle Burgen bearbeiten
+ Fundstelle hinzufügen
- BLFD-ID bearbeiten
+ Fundstelle hinzufügen
- BDA-Baudenkmal-ID bearbeiten
+ Fundstelle hinzufügen
- Google-Knowledge-Graph-Kennung bearbeiten
+ Fundstelle hinzufügen

Anwendung

Das ist LOD

Genug der Vorrede

Eckerker

Hocheingang

Eckquaderung
Buckelquader

Kapellenraum

Bergfried

Rechteckfenster

Wappenschild

Wohnbau

Eckturm
Schalenturm

Bruchstein-
mauerwerk

Ringmauer

Eckturm
Schalenturm

Besonderer Bautyp
 (zentralbauartiger, oktogonaler
 Seitenschiffschor), Aufgabe:
 Vergleichsbeispiele finden.

Load Save Undo Redo

Räumliche Kontexte

- Abgegangene Ausstattungskontext
- Ausstattungskontext
- Außenbau
- Axiale Grundstruktur
- Bauelementabschnittsbezogener Kontext
- Bauteilbezogener Kontext
- Befundkontext - Holter

Strukturhierarchie

- New York
- Nürnberg
 - Dominikanerkirche
 - Dreieinigkeitskirche
 - Germanisches Nationalmuseum
 - Heilig-Geist-Spital
 - Kunigundenkapelle
 - St. Georg
 - St. Jakob
 - St. Lorenz
- Wien

3D-Visualisierung Kartenansicht

Thematische Kontexte

- Begriffe für Ausstattung historischer Gebäude und Sammlungs
- Begriffe für Bauernhalt
- Begriffe für den Themenkomplex Archäologie
- Begriffe für den Themenkomplex Sakralbau
- Begriffe für Naturstein- und Wandmalereirestauration

Themen: NGK Themen: MonArch

- Akteur
- Anlage
- architektonische Gliederungseinheit
- Architekturfäche
- Bauelement
- Begrifflicher Gegenstand
- Darstellungsinhalt
- Eigenschaft
- Gebäude
- Gebäudeteil
- Geographischer Ort
- Infrastrukturelement
- Kartierungselement
- Konstruktionselement
- Material
- Materialschicht
- Merkmal
- Objekt
- Raum
- Sammlung
- Vorgang
- Zeitpunkt

Strukturtypen

- Anlage
- architektonische Gliederungseinheit
- Architekturfäche
- Ausstattung
- Bauelement
- Gebäude
- Gebäudeteil
- Geographischer Ort
- Infrastrukturelement
- Kartierungselement
- Konstruktionselement
- Materialschicht

Ergebnis: Digitale Dokumente Ergebnis: Strukturobjekte Ergebnis: Analoge Dokumente Ergebnis: Wissensobjekte Ergebnis: Alle Progress

Galerie Detail

0007.tif	0010.tif	05-nzs00880.pdf	10021-1.jpg	10021-541_541l.jpg	10021-60.jpg	10021-72.jpg	10021a.jpg	12001-35_aLH_NF6.jpg
12002-12_dW_MO.jpg	12006-41_d.jpg	12007-04_bLH.jpg	14-nzs00869.pdf	2007_aLH_SP1G1.jpg	2018_aLH_NP3.jpg	2033_aLH_NP6G1.jpg	2038_aLH_NP7G1.jpg	3058_aLH_N.jpg
3081a_b.jpg	3118bil_aLH_SF1G0.jpg	4076_aW_MWG2.jpg	4078_aW_MWG2.jpg	4135_aW.jpg	5020_1_2_XV_aCL_SP9.jpg	5020_1_2_X...aCL_SP9.jpg	5020_1_2_X...aCL_SP9.jpg	5115_02_aCL_NP2.jpg
5116_02_aCL_W.jpg	5117_01_aCL_W.jpg	6023_aW_TSBW.jpg	6040_aW_TSB.jpg	6062_aW_TSB.jpg	6071_aW_TS.jpg	6072_aW_TSA.jpg	6075_aW_TSA.jpg	6100_04_aW_TS.jpg

Klassische Ansicht Dynamische Ansicht

Gebäudestruktur

Topologie von Objekten
Instanzen von Klassen
Realdaten

Semantischer Graph mit
ontologischem Aufbau;

Räumliche / funktionale
Beziehungen der Objekte /
Teilobjekte;

Individuelles Objekt;

Ohne inhaltliche Auszeichnung der
Objekte;

Spezifische, separate Eingabe bei
jeder Anlage eines Datensatzes;

Nicht wiederverwendbar.

Sachthemen

kontrolliertes Vokabular
Klassendefinitionen
Stammdaten

Semantischer Graph mit
ontologischem Aufbau;

Thematische und begriffliche
Beziehungen von Konzepten /
Unterkonzepten;

Verallgemeinerbare Inhalte;

Ohne räumliche Verortung am
konkreten Objekt;

Vorformuliertes Wissen an einer
Stelle;

Wiederverwendbar.

Vokabular-Konzepte sind auch nur Klassen

“Von der Wiege bis zur Bahre, Vokabulare, Vokabulare”
(frei nach Wilhelm Busch)

Label

Literal

Zeichenfolge

- **Bsp.: „Buckelquader“**
B u c e e l q
u a d e r
- Erfolgreiche Suche:
„Buckelquader“, „BUCKELQUADER“, „Bucjkelquader“,
„Buckelquadermauerwerk“
evtl. auch:
„Buckelstein“
dann aber auch:
„Buckelblattkapitell“
- Erfolglose Suche:
„Bossenquader“, „Bossenwerk“, „Rohbosse“, „Prellbossen-
quader“, „querry-faced ashlar“, „sillar almohadillado“
- Suche aller Arten von „Mauerstein“ unter Einbe-
ziehung von „Buckelquader“:
fast unmöglich

Ressource

Konzept

URI

- **Bsp.: „Buckelquader“**
https://www.uni-bamberg.de/kdwt/vocab#c_8cf58090
- Erfolgreiche Suche:
„Buckelquader“, „BUCKELQUADER“, „Bucjkelquader“, „Bu-
ckelstein“, „Bossenquader“, „querry-faced ashlar“, „sillar almo-
hadillado“
aber **nicht**:
„Buckelblattkapitell“
- Erfolgreiche Suche unter Einbeziehung verwandter
Konzepte:
„Bossenwerk“, „Rohbosse“, „Buckelquadermauerwerk“
- Erfolgreiche Suche unter Einbeziehung von Speziali-
sierungen (child-nodes):
„Kissenbuckelquader“, „Rohbossenquader“ ...
- Erfolgreiche Suche aller Arten von „Mauerstein“ unter
Einbeziehung von „Buckelquader“:
„Buckelquader“, „Bossenquader“, „Kissenbuckelquader“, „Glatt-
quader“, „Eckquader“, „Bruchstein“, „Backstein“, „Klinker“ ...

Top of the AAT hierarchies

.... Objects Facet

..... Components (hierarchy name)

..... components (objects parts)

..... <components by specific context>

..... **architectural elements**

..... <structural elements and components for structural elements>

..... structural elements

..... structural assemblies

..... arcades (structural assemblies)

..... blind arcades

..... interlacing arcades

..... riwaqs

..... <spanning and projecting structural elements>

..... <arches and arch components>

..... arches

..... <arches by form>

..... [*weitere*]

..... semicircular arches

..... [*weitere*]

..... <arches by form: construction>

..... <arches by form: hinging>

..... <arches by form: number of centers>

..... <arches by form: plan>

..... [*weitere*]

Top of the AAT hierarchies

.... Objects Facet

..... Components (hierarchy name)

..... components (objects parts)

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..... <structural elements and components for structural elements>

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..... arcades (structural assemblies)

..... **blind arcades**

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..... riwaqs

..... <spanning and projecting structural elements>

..... <arches and arch components>

..... arches

..... <arches by form>

..... [weitere]

..... semicircular arches

..... [weitere]

..... <arches by form: construction>

..... <arches by form: hinging>

..... <arches by form: number of centers>

..... <arches by form: plan>

..... [weitere]

Note: Architectural elements that are part of the structure of a building, **as opposed to** elements that are **decorative**.

Note: Arcades closed at the back and serving **only as decorative** features.

Uuups
👉 Vererbung!

Top of the AAT hierarchies

.... Objects Facet

..... Components (hierarchy name)

..... components (objects parts)

..... <components by specific context>

..... architectural elements

..... <structural elements and components for structural elements>

..... structural elements

..... structural assemblies

..... arcades (structural assemblies)

..... blind arcades

..... interlacing arcades

..... riwaqs

..... <spanning and projecting structural elements>

..... <arches and arch components>

..... **arches**

..... <arches by form>

..... [weitere]

..... **semicircular arches**

..... [weitere]

..... <arches by form: construction>

..... <arches by form: hinging>

..... <arches by form: number of centers>

..... <arches by form: plan>

..... [weitere]

Note: Structural elements, typically curved, **spanning openings and transmitting vertical loads** to either side of the opening; also, structural elements or freestanding structures that resemble arches or act structurally like arches.

Uuups
👉 Vererbung!

transitiv

Beispiel für

Familiengruft des Johann Paulus Herring (Brünn)

tragendes Gewölbe (de), vault acting as a support (en), voûte-support (fr)

Trichtergewölbe (de), pendant vault (en), bóveda normanda (es), voûte pendante (fr), volta normanna (it)

trojdičná klenba (cs), dreiteiliges Gewölbe (de), tripartite vault (en), voûte à trois quartiers (fr)

überhöhtes Gewölbe (de), surmounted vault (en), voûte à sommet surhaussé (fr)

umgekehrtes Gewölbe (de), inverted barrel vault (en), voûte en berceau renversé (fr)

valená klenba (cs), Tonnengewölbe (de), barrel vault (en), bóveda de cañón (es), voûte en berceau (fr)

vějířová klenba (cs), Fächergewölbe (engere Bedeutung) (de), fan vault (en), bóveda palmiforme (es), voûte en éventails (fr)

Verstärkungsgewölbe (de), reinforcing vault (en), voûte de renfort (fr)

vertikales Gewölbe (de), vertical vault (en), voûte verticale (fr)

verzogenes Gewölbe (de), broken rib vault (en), voûte tourante (fr)

Vierungsgewölbe (de), crossing vault (en), voûte de croisée (fr)

Wallgewölbe (de), rampart vault (en), voûte de rempart (fr)

žebrová klenba (cs), Rippengewölbe (de), rib vault (en), bóveda nervada (es), voûte à nervures (fr), volta a costoloni (it)

- Diagonalrippengewölbe (de), diagonal-ribbed vault (en), voûte à nervures diagonales (fr)
- dreistrahliges Rippengewölbe (de), tripartite ribbed vault (en), voûte a tierceron (fr)
- Flechtrippengewölbe (de), lierne vaulting (en), voûte à liernes et à tiercerons doublés (fr)
- Parallelrippengewölbe (de), vault with parallel ribs (en), bóveda nervada en paralelo (es), voûte à nervures parallèles (fr), volta a nervature

Rippengewölbe

žebrová klenba (cs), Rippengewölbe...

žebrová klenba (cs), Rippengewölbe... https://www.uni-bamberg.de/kdwt/vocab#_c_b505b3b9

skos:prefLabel

- žebrová klenba
- Rippengewölbe
- rib vault
- bóveda nervada
- voûte à nervures
- volta a costoloni

skos:altLabel

- rib-and-panel-vaulting
- ribbed vault
- voûte à nervurée
- voûte à portantes
- volta a nervature

Notes:

skos:definition

Ein von Rippen getragenes Gewölbe, z. B. Kreuz-, Sterngewölbe, Netzgewölbe, Fächergewölbe, Domikalgewölbe u. dergl. (Gewölbeformen). In der Spätzeit der Gotik gibt es auch Gewölbe mit nichttragenden Stuckrippen, die nur formal als R. bezeichnet werden können; Zweischichtengewölbe, deren Rippen frei unter der selbsttragenden Gewölbeschale verlaufen, ferner frei nach unten durchhängende R. (Abhängling 1) und R. mit gewundener Reihung. [Koepl/Binding 2016]

Im engeren Sinne ein Kreuzrippengewölbe im weiteren Sinne jedes berippte Gewölbe, in dem die häufig stückierten Rippen der Gewölbeschale nur aufgelegt sind, um eine ornamentale Wirkung zu erzielen.

Rippengewölbe kommen als Kreuzgewölbe, als Fächergewölbe, als kuppelartig gekrümmte oder als tonnenartig gebogene Gewölbe vor. Durch die Einführung der tragenden Rippen erübrigte sich die schwierige Mauerung der Grate, denn man konnte nun das Mauerwerk den Rippen auflegen bzw. in ihre Nuten einfügen. Diese Neuerung war eine entscheidende Voraussetzung für die Entstehung der Gotik. Einer der großen Vorzüge des Rippengewölbes ist seine vielseitige Verwendbarkeit für die Einwölbung polygonaler und unregelmäßiger Grundflächen, z. B. von Apsiden und Chorumgängen. [Glossarium Artis]

ResView TermView Code

SKOS-CONCEPT:

https://hist-arch-vocab.org/bvha#c_8cf58090

prefLabel:

„**Buckelquader**“ @de

„quarry-faced ashlar“ @en

„carreau à bossage“ @fr

„sillar almohadillado“ @es

altLabel:

„**Bossenquader**“ @de

„Buckelstein“ @de

definition:

„Ein vierseitig exakt behauener Quader, dessen Stirnseite bzw. Spiegel mit einem vorspringenden Buckel (»Bosse«; daher auch die synonyme Bezeichnung Bossenquader) versehen ist. [...] (Wörterbuch der Burgen, Schlösser und Festungen).“ @de

Buckelquader, Buckelstein, Bossenquader; Quader, dessen Vorderseite nur roh behauen ist und daher mehr oder weniger stark vorspringt. Um exaktes Versetzen zu ermöglichen, erhalten die B. meist einen schmalen Randschlag mit gerader Kante (Koepf / Binding 2016).“ @de

...

2m

Quellennachweis Burgenwörterbuch @de

Böhme, Horst Wolfgang et al. (Hrsg.): Wörterbuch der Burgen, Schlösser und Festungen, Heidelberg: arthistoricum.net-ART-Books, 2020.
<https://doi.org/10.11588/arthistoricum.535>

Quellennachweis Koepf / Binding 2016 @de

Koepf, Hans - Binding, Günther: Bildwörterbuch der Architektur, Stuttgart 2022.

Modellierung eines Konzeptes gemäß W3C-Empfehlungen für SKOS am Beispiel des Begriffs „Buckelquader“ im Bamberger Vokabular für historische Architektur.

...
 „Buckelquader, Buckelstein, Bossenquader; Quader, dessen Vorderseite nur roh behauen ist und daher mehr oder weniger stark vorspringt. Um exaktes Versetzen zu ermöglichen, erhalten die B. meist einen schmalen Randschlag mit gerader Kante (Koepf / Binding 2016).“ @de

„Quader mit Randschlag und grob bearbeiteter Vorderseite.“ (Glossarium Artis, Bd. 3, Bögen und Mauerwerk) @de

inScheme:

Quellennachweis Koepf / Binding 2016 @de
 Quellennachweis Burgenwörterbuch @de
 Quellennachweis Glossarium Artis @de

broader:

„Quader“ @de

narrower:

„Kissenbuckelquader“ @de
 „Prallbuckelquader“ @de

related:

„Buckelquadermauerwerk“ @de
 „Bosse“ @de

closeMatch:

<https://d-nb.info/gnd/4445312-7>

Modellierung eines Konzeptes gemäß W3C-Empfehlungen für SKOS am Beispiel des Begriffs „Buckelquader“ im Bamberger Vokabular für historische Architektur.

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inScheme:

Quellennachweis Koeopf / Binding 2016 @de
 Quellennachweis Burgenwörterbuch @de
 Quellennachweis Glossarium Artis @de

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inScheme:

Quellennachweis Koeopf / Binding 2016 @de

Quellennachweis Burgenwörterbuch @de

Quellennachweis Glossarium Artis @de

broader:

„Quader“ @de

narrower:

„Kissenbuckelquader“ @de

„Prallbuckelquader“ @de

related:

„Buckelquadermauerwerk“ @de

„Bosse“ @de

closeMatch:

<https://d-nb.info/gnd/4445312-7> ○

← 2m

Modellierung eines Konzeptes gemäß W3C-Empfehlungen für SKOS am Beispiel des Begriffs „Buckelquader“ im Bamberger Vokabular für historische Architektur.

“Strukturtypen”

... umfassen alle (architektonischen) Objekte beliebigen Maßstabs mit definierter, begrenzter Ausdehnung, die strukturell bzw. “topologisch” lokalisiert werden können. Strukturtypen bezeichnen im weitesten Sinne die Kategorie von Objekten.

entspricht:

CIDOC-CRM **E22**, Human-Made Object

Dazu zählen nicht nur physisch vorhandene Objekte, wie Bauwerksgruppen, Gebäudeteile oder einzelne Konstruktionselemente, sondern auch abstrakte Objekte, wie ein Grundriss, Gliederungseinheiten oder Achsen.

entspricht:

CIDOC-CRM **E28**, Conceptual Object)

“Themen”

... sind Merkmale / Eigenschaften / Charakteristika von (architektonischen) Objekten, die räumlich nicht abgrenzbar sind und deshalb nicht strukturell bzw. “topologisch” verortet werden können. Themen sind im weitesten Sinne diejenigen Merkmale, die der Kategorisierung der “Objekte” dienen.

entspricht eingeschränkt:

CIDOC-CRM **E26**, Physical Feature)

Dazu zählen die Materialität, Form- und Farbeigenschaften, Erhaltungszustände, Bearbeitungsspuren, Schadensmerkmale, Konstruktionsarten

“Strukturtypen”

... umfassen alle (architektonischen) Objekte beliebigen Maßstabs mit definierter, begrenzter Ausdehnung, die strukturell bzw. “topologisch” lokalisiert werden können. Strukturtypen bezeichnen im weitesten Sinne die Kategorie von Objekten.

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entspricht:

CIDOC-CRM **E28**, Conceptual Object)

“Themen”

... sind im Sinne der Verwendung des Vokabulars im MonArch-Archivsystem bzw. dem MonArch-RDF-Datenmodell aber auch Vorgänge, wie Maßnahmen, Funktionen, Nutzungen, Akteure etc.

diese entsprechen diversen
CIDOC-CRM-Klassen

Bauwerksgruppe

Gruppierung mehrerer vollständiger Bauwerke: “städtischer Wohnblock”, “Akropolis”, “Burganlage”.

Bauwerk

Vollständiges oder zumindest vollständig gedachtes Bauwerk: “Klosterkirche”, “Jagdschloss”, “Schifffahrtskanal”, “Triumphbogen”.

B1

Build Work

Bauwerksteil

größere i.d.R. auch allein nutzbare Gebäudeeinheit, die sich i.d.R. sowohl aus “gefüllten” Bauwerkselementen wie auch den von ihnen umschlossenen “leeren” Räumen zusammensetzt: “Langhaus”, “Seitenflügel”, “Pronaos”.

B2

Morphological Building
Section

Bauwerkselement

größere “gefüllte” Gebäudeeinheit ohne umschlossene Räume: “Arkade”, “Außenwand”, “Postament”.

B3

Filled morph. building section

(umbauter) Raum

größere nicht materielle, “leere” Raumeinheit: “Altarraum”, “Kuppelsaal”, “Straßenraum”.

B4

Empty morph, building section

Bauwerkskomponente

kleinere “nicht weiter zerlegbare”, “gefüllte” Einheit, Bestandteil der Bauelemente: “Mauerquader”, “Kantholz”, “Mauerfuge”.

Architekturfläche

Ebene an der Grenze “gefüllter” Bauelemente und “leerer” Räume: “Bogenlaibung”, “Außenseite”

Subordination vs. Assoziation:

Phänomenbasiert statt begriffsbasiert:

Architekturspezifische Sichtweise:

Subordination vs. Assoziation

- Broader/narrower als Spezialisierung im engeren Sinne;
- Auffassung von related als gleichberechtigte Assoziation;

Sub-Properties dienen hier bspw. der Auszeichnung von Bestandteilen.

Phänomenbasierte Ontologie

- Maßgeblich ist **Bedeutungsgehalt**, nicht die **Begrifflichkeit**.

Architekturspezifische Sichtweise

- Sub-Properties dienen der architektur-spezifischen Auszeichnung von Subordinationen;
- Werden insbesondere bei langen Listen zur Vorklassifizierung von Unterbegriffen benutzt;
- Flexible Alternative zu hierarchy terms oder guide terms.

Topologische Zergliederung

Geometrie:

- Liefert Informationen zu Dimension, Maßstab, Verortung im Geokoordinatensystem;
- Liefert keine funktionalen und räumlichen Wechselbeziehungen sowie Bedeutungsinhalte.

Topologie:

- Liefert funktionale und räumliche Wechselbeziehungen sowie Bedeutungsinhalte;
- Liefert keine Informationen zu Dimension, Maßstab und Verortung im Geokoordinatensystem.

Geokoordinaten

Gesamtanlage:

- **Burg-Schloss:**
Wasserschloss
Vierflügelanlage
Dreiflügelanlage
- **Niederungslage:**
ohne Überhöhung
- **Adelsburg, landesherrliche Burg:**
Ministerialensitz
Stammsitz
Jagdschloss
- ...

*transitiv
(mehrere Elemente)*

Hauptturm:

- **Bergfried**
- **Grundriss:**
quadratisch
- **Aufriss:**
dreigeschossig

type

Vokabular

Erschließung:

- *Mauertreppe*

Wehr- und Schutzelement:

- *Hocheingang*

Funktionsraum:

- *Kellergewölbe*

Kapelle:

- *Bauteil im Hauptturm*
- *Sakralraum*

Mauer-Technik:

- *Eckquader*
- *Buckelquader*

Situationsphoto, Mauertreppe

Befundskizze, Hocheingang

Orthophoto, Buckelquader

Strukturgraph:

Themengraph:

Auszeichnung mit Eigenschaften:

- Spatial symbolic entities im Strukturgraphen haben keine Eigenschaften;
- Qualitative Auszeichnungen sind Verweise (is instance of) auf das Vokabular (Themengraph);
- Es gibt zwei Beziehungsarten zwischen Instanzen und Klassen:
- Die **type-Beziehung** bezeichnet, was die jeweilige entity eigentlich ist und entspricht **RDF:type** bzw. Wikidata **P32** (ist ein/e bzw. is instance of);
- Die **topical reference** weist der entity weitere Eigenschaften zu.

Beziehungsarten:

- **part-of-Beziehung:** Die Randkapellen sind Teil des Chorhauptes; Das Chorhaupt ist Teil des Chores.
—————→
- **belongs-to-Beziehung:** Der Pfeiler gehört zu jeweils zwei Jochen des Seitenschiffes und gehört zu jeweils zwei weiteren Jochen des Mittelschiffes.
- - - - -→
- **connects-Beziehung:** Die beiden Randkapellen sind räumlich und konstruktiv benachbart bzw. miteinander verbunden.
◀.....▶

Part-Of-Beziehung:

- Gerichtet;
- ähnlich SKOS:broader;
- Zeigt existenzielle Abhängigkeit;
- Eindeutige Zuordnung.

Belongs-To-Beziehung:

- Gerichtet;
- ähnlich SKOS:broader;
- Zeigt wechselseitige Zugehörigkeit;
- Mehrfache Zuordnung möglich.

Connects-Beziehung:

- Ungerichtet;
- Entspricht sinngemäß SKOS:related und entstammt dem BIM-Kontext;
- Zeigt wechselseitige direkte räumliche und konstruktive Verbindungen.

Beziehungsarten:

- **part-of-Beziehung:** Die Randkapellen sind Teil des Chorhauptes;
Das Chorhaupt ist Teil des Chores.
—————→
- **belongs-to-Beziehung:** Der Pfeiler gehört zu jeweils zwei Jochen des Seitenschiffes und gehört zu jeweils zwei weiteren Jochen des Mittelschiffes.
- - - - -→
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◀.....▶

Wikidata P361
CIDOC-CRM: P46i

Wikidata P1382 (?)
CIDOC-CRM: ???

Befundzuordnung

Problematik des streng hierarchischen Raum-/Befundbuches:

Entweder die Wände (bei raumbezogener und wandflächen-bezogener Anordnung) oder die Räume (bei bauteilbezogener Anordnung) sind nur mittelbar, durch Querverweise darstellbar.

Befundzuordnung

Flächenbezogene und daher auch räumliche Befundzuordnung:

Flächenbezogene und daher auch bauelementbezogene Befundzuordnung:

Befundzuordnung

Synthese der flächenbezogenen und daher auch raum- und bauelementbezogenen Befundzuordnung:

Grundregel der topologischen Modellierung von Architektur

Bauwerksgruppe

Gruppierung mehrerer vollständiger Bauwerke.

Bauwerk

Vollständiges oder zumindest vollständig gedachtes Bauwerk.

Bauwerksteil

Größere i.d.R. auch allein nutzbare Gebäudeeinheit, die sich i.d.R. sowohl aus “gefüllten” Bauwerkselementen wie auch den von ihnen umschlossenen “leeren” Räumen zusammensetzt.

Bauwerkselement

größere “gefüllte” Gebäudeeinheit ohne umschlossene Räume.

(umbauter) Raum

größere nicht materielle, “leere” Raumeinheit.

Bauwerkskomponente

kleinere “nicht weiter zerlegbare”, “gefüllte” Einheit, Bestandteil der Bauelemente.

Architekturfläche

Ebene an der Grenze “gefüllter” Bauelemente und “leerer” Räume.

Modellierungsbeispiel für Verortung von künstlerischer Ausstattung

um 1250

um 1350

um 1500

Modellierungsbeispiel für das Nebeneinander unterschiedlicher Bauzustände

Modellierungsbeispiel für Rekonstruktionsvarianten aus dem archäologischen Befund

Schloss Hofstetten:

- **Burg-Schloss:**
Wasserschloss
Vierflügelanlage
Dreiflügelanlage
- **Niederungslage:**
ohne Überhöhung
- **Adelsburg, landesherrliche Burg:**
Ministerialsitz
Stammsitz
Jagdschloss
- ...

transitiv
(mehrere Elemente)

Hauptturm:

- **Bergfried**
- **Grundriss:**
quadratisch
- **Aufriss:**
dreigeschossig

Kapelle:

- **Bauteil im Hauptturm**
- **Sakralraum**

Ereignis

- **historisch**
Ersterwähnung
- **genau**
1122
- *Burkhard von Hofstetten als Urkundenzeuge unter den Eichstätter Ministerialen erwähnt*
- **historisch**
Überlieferung/Archivalien
indirekt

Ereignis

- **baulich**
Errichtung
- **zwischen, vor genau**
1122 *und näherungsweise*
1250
- *Errichtung der Burg unter den Ministerialen von Hofstetten (später von Geyern).*
- **historisch**
Überlieferung
indirekt *bau- und kunstgeschichtlich Analogie absolut*

Ereignis

- **historisch**
Erwähnung
- **genau**
1602
- *Erwähnung der Burgkapelle St. Elisabeth durch Vitus Priefer*
- **historisch**
Überlieferung/Archivalien
direkt


```

@prefix wd: <http://wikibase.svc/entity/> .
@prefix wds: <http://wikibase.svc/entity/statement/> .
@prefix wdt: <http://wikibase.svc/prop/direct/> .
@prefix p: <http://wikibase.svc/prop/> .
@prefix ps: <http://wikibase.svc/prop/statement/> .
  
```

Linked Open Data

Classes, Instances and Properties

David Rasp, CC BY 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

Classes, Instances and Properties

Fotograv. - Generalstabens
Litografiska Anstalt Stockholm, Public
domain, via Wikimedia Commons

Linked Data is based on RDF

image via ontotext.com

Linked Data

Linked Data Principles

Linked Data

The Semantic Web isn't just about putting data on the web. It is about making links, so that a person or machine can explore the web of data. With linked data, when you have some of it, you can find other, related, data.

Like the web of hypertext, the web of data is constructed with documents on the web. However, unlike the web of hypertext, where links are relationships anchors in hypertext documents written in HTML, for data they links between arbitrary things described by RDF,. The URIs identify any kind of object or concept. But for HTML or RDF, the same expectations apply to make the web grow:

1. Use URIs as names for things
2. Use HTTP URIs so that people can look up those names.
3. When someone looks up a URI, provide useful information, using the standards (RDF*, SPARQL)
4. Include links to other URIs. so that they can discover more things.

from <https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html>

5 Star Data

via <https://5stardata.info/> and <https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html>

Linked Open Data Cloud

OGC GeoSPARQL Ontology

Med, Michal & Kremen, Petr. (2017). Context-based ontology for urban data integration. 457-461. DOI: 10.1145/3151759.3151838.

<https://opengeospatial.github.io/ogc-geosparql/geosparql11/spec.html>

GeoSPARQL Query Language

An extension of SPARQL to map relations between geometries

SPARQL Query Language

SPARQL Query Language

from <https://wordlift.io/blog/en/entity/sparql/>

Linked Open Data in Action

(Examples from the Humanities ...)

nomisma.org

nomisma.org Browse IDs Research Tools APIs Documentation Ontology SPARQL Datasets

Laodicea ad Mare (Mint, Concept)

Canonical URI: http://nomisma.org/id/laodiceia_ad_mare

Labels

Preferred Label: Laodicea ad Mare (en), Λαττακίη (fr), Λατᾶκια (es), Laodicea (it), Λατᾶκια (de), Λαττακία (el) **Additional labels ▶**

Alternate Label: Laodicea pros Mare (en)

Definitions

en The mint at the ancient site of Laodicea in Syria.

Geospatial Data

URI: http://nomisma.org/id/laodiceia_ad_mare#this

Latitude: 35.516967

Longitude: 35.783333

Part Of: http://nomisma.org/id/seleucia_and_pieria#this

Relations

Broader Concept: http://nomisma.org/id/seleucia_and_pieria

Close Match: <http://collection.britishmuseum.org/id/place/x48252>

Close Match: <http://id-nb.info/gnd/4270543-5>

Close Match: <http://dbpedia.org/resource/Latakia>

Close Match: <http://sws.geonames.org/173576/>

Close Match: <http://sws.geonames.org/8445122/>

Close Match: <http://viaf.org/viaf/135413368>

Close Match: <http://vocab.getty.edu/tn/7022280>

Close Match: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q200030>

Close Match: <https://pleiades.stoa.org/places/688290>

Close Match: <https://www.freebase.com/m/01bamp>

Concept Scheme: <http://nomisma.org/id/>

Miscellaneous

Part Of: http://nomisma.org/id/greek_numismatics

Part Of: http://nomisma.org/id/roman_numismatics

Part Of: http://nomisma.org/id/roman_provincial_numismatics

Export

Linked Data: [GitHub File](#) [RDF/XML](#) [RDF/TTL](#) [JSON-LD](#)

Geographic Data: [KML](#) [GeoJSON](#)

Leaflet | Map data © OpenStreetMap contributors, CC-BY-SA, Imagery © Mapbox

Type	AuthorityID	MintID	DenominationID	Date1	Example
Selected Coins (part 1) 36	Seleucia I Number	Laodicea ad Mare	Tetradrachm	300 BCE - 200 BCE	
Selected Coins (part 1) 27	Seleucia I Number	Laodicea ad Mare	Diachme	300 BCE - 200 BCE	
Selected Coins (part 1) 257	Antiochia I Obol	Laodicea ad Mare	Tetradrachm	201 BCE - 201 BCE	
Selected Coins (part 1) 255	Antiochia I Obol	Laodicea ad Mare	Diachme	201 BCE - 201 BCE	
Selected Coins (part 1) 302	Antiochia I Obol	Laodicea ad Mare	Tetradrachm	278 BCE - 201 BCE	
Selected Coins (part 1) 515	Antiochia I Obol	Laodicea ad Mare	Tetradrachm	201 BCE - 248 BCE	
Selected Coins (part 1) 305	Seleucia II Obolus	Laodicea ad Mare	Tetradrachm	230 BCE - 233 BCE	
Prose Coins		Laodicea ad Mare	Tetradrachm	205 BCE - 205 BCE	

Nomisma | http://nomisma.org/id/laodiceia_ad_mare

kerameikos.org

Kerameikos.org | [Browse](#) | [Research Tools](#) | [Ontology](#) | [APIs](#) | [Documentation](#) | [SPARQL](#) | [Databases](#) |

Objects of this Typology | Quantitative Analysis

Bowl (Shape, Concept)

Canonical URI: <http://kerameikos.org/id/bowl>

Labels

Preferred Label Bowl (en), bol (fr), catola (it), Schüssel (de), λικάνη (el) | Additional labels ▶

Definitions

- en The term bowl is used to designate a plain, open shape without handles.
- de Begriff zur Beschreibung einer einfachen, offenen Form ohne Henkel.
- el Ο δίσκος περιλαμβάνει ένα ασύμ, ανοικτό αγγείο χωρίς χερούλι.

Relations

- Exact Match** <http://vocab.getty.edu/aid/300203986>
- Exact Match** <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q1131988>
- Exact Match** <https://www.britishmuseum.org/topic/lexicon/term/x/5597>
- Reference** <https://zenon.dainet.org/Record/000926820>

Data Provenance ▶

Data Export: [RDF/XML](#) | [TTL](#) | [JSON-LD](#)

Map showing the distribution of Bowl finds across the Mediterranean region. Legend: Place (blue), Findspot (red).

Objects of this Typology

These objects are associated by artist signature or scholarly attribution by analyzing artistic similarities. Only those with images are shown below, but all objects related to the concept are queried for other visualizations and data downloads.

Records 1 to 48 of 310

1 2 3 4 Next ▶ 7 ▶

Kerameikos | <http://kerameikos.org/id/bowl>

Linked Open Samian Ware | Samian Research

LEIZA Linked Open Samian Ware | <https://rgzm.github.io/samian-lod/>

Linked Ogham Data

Linked Ogham Data | <http://ogham.link>

NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph

 NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph | SPARQL | Cypher | **Collections** | Repositories | Terminologies | Manual

A collection is an individual set of research data imported into the knowledge graph. Each collection is identified by a URI starting with <https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/collection/>. Each collection belongs to a [research data repository](#) where its data has been published.

Information about collections is stored in the RDF graph <https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/collection/>.

collection	name	repository	license
1 n4oc:1	Ur- und Frühgeschichtliche Sammlung der FAU	wd:Q124695065	
2 n4oc:2	Paläontologischen Sammlung der FAU Geowissenschaftliche Sammlung der FAU	wd:Q124695065	
3 n4oc:3	Graphische Sammlung der FAU	wd:Q124695065	
4 n4oc:4	Musikinstrumentensammlung der FAU	wd:Q124695065	
5 n4oc:5	Medizinische Sammlung der FAU	wd:Q124695065	
6 n4oc:6	Schulgeschichtliche Sammlung der FAU und Schulmuseum	wd:Q124695065	
7 n4oc:7	KENOM Virtuelles Münzportal (via LIDO)	wd:Q21040628	
8 n4oc:8	Samian Research Database	wd:Q22661177	https://www.hbz-nrw.de/produkte/open-access/lizenzen/dppl/mdppl/m-DPPL_v3_en_11-2008
9 n4oc:9	Linked Open Ogham	wd:Q22661177	http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
10 n4oc:10	African Red Slip Ware	wd:Q22661177	http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
11 n4oc:11	Digitale Sammlungen der Museen der Klassikstiftung Weimar	wd:Q124536091	
12 n4oc:12	Graphische Sammlung des Germanisches National Museum	wd:Q478695	
13 n4oc:13	KENOM (via Nomisma)	wd:Q24578999	

N4O Knowledge Graph

<https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/sparql>

Samian Research Database

<https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/collection/8>

Loaded into the graph at 2024-09-24T09:11:00+00:00 with 7764422 triples.

Homepage: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13832255>

Quell-Repository: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q22661177>

Lizenz der Daten: https://www.hbz-nrw.de/produkte/open-access/lizenzen/dppl/mdppl/m-DPPL_v3_en_11-2008

Please use SPARQL to get more information about the collection such as used classes and used properties.

7'764'422

```

@prefix dcat: <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#> .
@prefix dcterm: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/> .
@prefix foaf: <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/> .
@prefix j: <http://schema.org/> .
@prefix j:4: <http://purl.org/spar/fabio/> .
@prefix skos: <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#> .
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .

<https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/collection/8> a j:4:Database,
    dcat:Dataset ;
    dcterm:isPartOf <https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/collection/> ;
    dcterm:issued "2024-09-24T09:11:00+00:00"^^xsd:dateTime ;
    dcterm:license "https://www.hbz-nrw.de/produkte/open-access/lizenzen/dppl/mdppl/m-DPPL_v3_en_11-2008" ;
    j:2:name "Samian Research Database" ;
    skos:notation "8" ;
    foaf:homepage <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13832255> .
    
```

African Red Slip Ware

<https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/collection/10>

Loaded into the graph at 2024-09-06T08:26:00+00:00 with 64531 triples.

Homepage: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5642751>

Quell-Repository: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q22661177>

Lizenz der Daten: <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Please use SPARQL to get more information about the collection such as used classes and used properties.

64'531

```

@prefix dcat: <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#> .
@prefix dcterm: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/> .
@prefix foaf: <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/> .
@prefix j:2: <http://schema.org/> .
@prefix j:4: <http://purl.org/spar/fabio/> .
@prefix skos: <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#> .
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .

<https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/collection/10> a j:4:Database,
    dcat:Dataset ;
    dcterm:isPartOf <https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/collection/> ;
    dcterm:issued "2024-09-06T08:26:00+00:00"^^xsd:dateTime,
        "2024-09-06T07:00:00+00:00"^^xsd:dateTime,
        "2024-09-06T08:26:00+00:00"^^xsd:dateTime ;
    dcterm:license "http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/" ;
    j:2:name "African Red Slip Ware" ;
    skos:notation "10" ;
    foaf:homepage <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5642751> .
    
```

Linked Open Ogham

<https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/collection/9>

Loaded into the graph at 2024-09-06T08:26:00+00:00 with 102114 triples.

Homepage: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4765603>

Quell-Repository: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q22661177>

Lizenz der Daten: <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Please use SPARQL to get more information about the collection such as used classes and used properties.

102'114

```

@prefix dcat: <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#> .
@prefix dcterm: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/> .
@prefix foaf: <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/> .
@prefix j:2: <http://schema.org/> .
@prefix j:4: <http://purl.org/spar/fabio/> .
@prefix skos: <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#> .
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .

<https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/collection/9> a j:4:Database,
    dcat:Dataset ;
    dcterm:isPartOf <https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/collection/> ;
    dcterm:issued "2024-09-06T08:26:00+00:00"^^xsd:dateTime,
        "2024-09-06T07:00:00+00:00"^^xsd:dateTime,
        "2024-09-06T08:26:00+00:00"^^xsd:dateTime ;
    dcterm:license "http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/" ;
    j:2:name "Linked Open Ogham" ;
    skos:notation "9" ;
    foaf:homepage <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4765603> .
    
```

NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph SPARQL | Cypher

SPARQL endpoint `/api/sparql` (see documentation)

```

1 PREFIX geosparql: <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#>
2 PREFIX lado: <http://archaeology.link/ontology#>
3 PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
4 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
5 SELECT ?item ?label ?geo (count(?item) AS ?count) WHERE {
6   ?ic lado:hasKilnsite <http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_pc_2000042> .
7   ?ic lado:disclosedAt ?item .
8   ?item geosparql:hasGeometry ?geom_obj .
9   ?geom_obj geosparql:asWKT ?geo .
10  OPTIONAL {?item rdfs:label ?label}
11 } GROUP BY ?item ?label ?geo ORDER BY DESC(?count)

```


N4O Knowledge Graph

<https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/sparql>

item	label	geo	count
http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1001015	"Reims"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(4.033333 49.25)"@geo:wkt:Literal	"22"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1001549	"Les Allieux"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(5.090895 49.192956)"@geo:wkt:Literal	"12"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1002190	"Valkenburg"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(4.433332 52.18333)"@geo:wkt:Literal	"8"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1001633	"Vechten"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(5.168262 52.060794)"@geo:wkt:Literal	"17"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1001255	"Tongeren"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(5.46484 50.78054)"@geo:wkt:Literal	"17"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1001351	"Voorburg"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(4.349213 52.060064)"@geo:wkt:Literal	"15"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1002376	"Trier"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(6.633333 49.75)"@geo:wkt:Literal	"15"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1000902	"Niederbieber"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(7.471947 50.467026)"@geo:wkt:Literal	"15"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1000302	"Rouen"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(1.083333 49.43333)"@geo:wkt:Literal	"14"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1000561	"Bavay"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(3.7937199999999995 50.29828)"@geo:wkt:Literal	"14"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1003939	"Zugmantel"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(8.203443 50.189704)"@geo:wkt:Literal	"14"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1004150	"Forêt de Complègne"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(2.883333 49.366664)"@geo:wkt:Literal	"13"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1002021	"Zwammerdam"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(5.2099998)"@geo:wkt:Literal	"13"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1003111	"Heerlen"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(5.983333 50.900001)"@geo:wkt:Literal	"13"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1000136	"London"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(-0.09184 51.51279)"@geo:wkt:Literal	"12"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1000062	"York"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(-1.083333 53.96667)"@geo:wkt:Literal	"12"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1000080	"Colchester"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(0.899999 51.883338)"@geo:wkt:Literal	"12"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1001626	"Le Pont-des-Rèmes"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(4.949999 49.1333)"@geo:wkt:Literal	"12"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1000157	"Dalheim"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(6.259722 49.540828)"@geo:wkt:Literal	"12"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1000045	"Xanten"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(6.45297 51.65877)"@geo:wkt:Literal	"12"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1003244	"Enfield"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(-0.06 51.643177)"@geo:wkt:Literal	"11"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1000375	"Lincoln"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(-0.533333 53.233333)"@geo:wkt:Literal	"11"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>

NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph

SPARQL

SPARQL endpoint [/api/sparql](https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/sparql) (see [documentation](#))

TOTAL 18 ARS OBJECTS LOAD!

Sort attributes
 label inventory number

Result style attributes
 boxes list

Active filter

object shape
bowl

object condition
complete

Filter labels & identifiers

Q enter search string

Filter keywords

- Object Type
- Object Shape
- Object Material
- Object Condition
- Object Manufacturing Type
- Object Findspot
- Object Residence
- Object Period
- Object Group
- Object Statement
- Getty AAT
- Wikidata
- Feature Type
- Feature Manufacturing Type
- Feature Statement
- Feature Observation Item Class
- Feature Observation Item


```

1 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
2 PREFIX crm: <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/>
3 PREFIX ars: <http://ars3D/documentation/ontology/arsonto#>
4
5 SELECT DISTINCT ?obj ?label ?identifier WHERE {
6   ?obj rdfs:label ?label.
7   ?obj crm:P1_is_identified_by ?id42.
8   ?id42 rdfs:label ?identifier.
9   ?obj ars:hasShape ars:acd64083-d3ab-4e1d-91d8-f2b043000001.
10  ?obj crm:P44_has_condition ars:4b97fd03-3423-48e1-a61c-c02f21000001.
11 } ORDER BY ASC(?label)

```

N4O Knowledge Graph

<https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/sparql>

obj	label	identifier
1 <http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/95c8cc98-06a8-4bb6-a85b-fcc93c98689f>	'bowl with Abraham and Isaac'@en	'0.40573'@en
2 <http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/4dc14582-fb7f-4d5e-a14d-79271ee733a3>	'bowl with Adam and Eve'@en	'0.39768'@en
3 <http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/2c81898a-647b-4527-a3ba-544e918460ca>	'bowl with Hercules and Minerva'@en	'0.40576'@en
4 <http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/595257bc-f279-49d0-bd69-9fbca4d63dab>	'bowl with Hercules and the apples of the Hesperides'@en	'0.39780'@en
5 <http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/8dd07582-bdda-4e94-b4dc-e944b160cf51>	'bowl with Lazarus'@en	'0.40868'@en
6 <http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/9bbd03c5-33a3-4682-90f1-4ddd6c7fe57d>	'bowl with Minerva'@en	'0.40866'@en
7 <http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/47def21b-ca45-4dbd-9eac-899956149b1d>	'bowl with animal hunt'@en	'0.40761'@en
8 <http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/6b46eb63-a258-4076-963f-49b2d0a8530f>	'bowl with boat and baskets'@en	'0.40719'@en
9 <http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/10e6f99f-172d-47ba-aa3b-4ff348de188c>	'bowl with erots and grapes'@en	'0.41944'@en
10 <http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/09114937-85ef-4bf5-bca0-351696030cd2>	'bowl with fishes'@en	'0.39846'@en
11 <http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/e4becf0-90de-4c14-b40a-34c1962c04bc>	'bowl with foxes and trees'@en	'0.41945'@en
12 <http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/6b5c47ad-82d9-4e20-a2f1-57b357a1df22>	'bowl with hare and baskets'@en	'0.40742'@en
13 <http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/a8437964-4402-4c7e-ba58-2b80b585e8c0>	'bowl with lions and Kantharos'@en	'0.40574'@en
14 <http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/1a212bd2-666e-41f3-871f-0a33de751576>	'bowl with martyr and bear'@en	'0.41911'@en
15 <http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/29282a82-c498-4ec7-ab07-94846a9f84ac>	'bowl with men and lion'@en	'0.41752'@en
16 <http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/9385f9d6-2523-4c71-a520-07544a35b8f5>	'bowl with palmetto'@en	'0.40747'@en
17 <http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/554ce8ce-fa32-4cb1-8466-31500e9ab32>	'bowl with quadriga and bear'@en	'0.39896'@en
18 <http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/64c2cb47-bbfc-44c4-9108-3dd6859150f0>	'bowl with sitting human, lion and leopard'@en	'0.39895'@en

Showing 1 to 18 of 18 entries

< 1 >

NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph

SPARQL endpoint `/api/sparql` (see [documentation](#))

```

1 PREFIX geosparql: <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#>
2 PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
3 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
4 PREFIX oghamonto: <http://ontology.ogham.link/>
5 SELECT ?item ?label ?geo WHERE {
6   ?item a oghamonto:OghamSite.
7   ?item rdfs:label ?label.
8   ?item geosparql:hasGeometry ?item_geom.
9   ?item_geom geosparql:asWKT ?geo.
10 }
    
```

Annascaul (Ogham Site)
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000003>

The Annascaul (Ogham Site) resource is powered by Static GeoPubby generated using the SPARQLing Unicons OGS Plugin

Search: Download options: [normal](#) [TTL](#) [JSON](#) [Download](#)

Property	Value
<code>exactMatch (oghamonto:exactMatch)</code>	<code>OS40000003 (lod:OS40000003) [s]</code>
<code>label_bare (oghamonto:label_bare)</code>	<code>Annascaul (lod:string)</code>
<code>label_country (oghamonto:label_country)</code>	<code>Ireland (lod:string)</code>
<code>label_county (oghamonto:label_county)</code>	<code>Kerry (lod:string)</code>
<code>label_province (oghamonto:label_province)</code>	<code>Munster (lod:string)</code>
<code>label_switzerland (oghamonto:label_switzerland)</code>	<code>Annagge (lod:string)</code>
<code>oghamonto:oghamonto (oghamonto:oghamonto:oghamonto)</code>	<code>OS40000003 geom (lod:OS40000003_geom)</code>
<code>hasGeometry (pp:hasGeometry)</code>	<code>OS40000003_geom (lod:OS40000003_geom)</code>
<code>type (rdf:type)</code>	<code>OghamSite (oghamonto:OghamSite) [s]</code> <code>Place (Place) [s]</code>
<code>label (rdf:label)</code>	<code>Annascaul (Ogham Site) (lod:string) (oghamonto:oghamonto)</code>
<code>is_member (rdf:member) of</code>	<code>OghamSite instances Collection (lod:OghamSite_instances)</code> <code>Place instances Collection (lod:Place_instances)</code>

Property	Value
<code>creator (terms:creator)</code>	<code>0000-0001-2346-3031 (0000-0001-2346-3031) [s]</code>
<code>license (terms:license)</code>	<code>deed de (deed.de) [s]</code>
<code>oghamonto:oghamonto (oghamonto:oghamonto)</code>	<code>0000-0001-2346-3031 (0000-0001-2346-3031) [s]</code> <code>0000-0001-4498-2101 (0000-0001-4498-2101) [s]</code> <code>oghamonto:oghamonto (oghamonto:oghamonto)</code>
<code>isDataset (void:isDataset)</code>	<code>linked_ogham_ogham (lod:linked_ogham_ogham) [s640 geo:FeatureCollection]</code>
<code>oghamonto:oghamonto (oghamonto:oghamonto)</code>	<code>pythondotnet (lod:pythondotnet)</code>
<code>wasDerivedFrom (prov:wasDerivedFrom)</code>	<code>og_sparql (og_sparql) [s]</code>
<code>wasDerivedFrom (prov:wasDerivedFrom)</code>	<code>og_sparql (og_sparql) [s]</code>
<code>wasDerivedFrom (prov:wasDerivedFrom)</code>	<code>OS40000003_activity (lod:OS40000003_activity)</code>

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Table Response 231 results

item
1 <http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000001>
2 <http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000002>
3 <http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000003>
4 <http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000004>
5 <http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000005>
6 <http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000006>
7 <http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000007>
8 <http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000008>
9 <http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000009>
10 <http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000010>
11 <http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000011>
12 <http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000012>
13 <http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000013>
14 <http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000014>
15 <http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000015>
16 <http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000016>
17 <http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000017>
18 <http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000018>
19 <http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000019>
20 <http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000020>

Label

"Bennettsbridge (Ogham Site)"@en
"Drumlohan (Ogham Site)"@en
"Aghacarrible (Ogham Site)"@en
"Aghaleague (Ogham Site)"@en
"Aghascreabhagh (Ogham Site)"@en
"Aglish (Ogham Site)"@en
"Ahalisky (Ogham Site)"@en
"Annagap (Ogham Site)"@en
"Annascaul (Ogham Site)"@en
"Ardcanaght (Ogham Site)"@en
"Ardref (Ogham Site)"@en
"Ardocheasty (Ogham Site)"@en
"Ardrinane (Ogham Site)"@en
"Ardwanig (Ogham Site)"@en
"Arraglen (Ogham Site)"@en
"Aultagh (Ogham Site)"@en
"Ballineesteenig (Ogham Site)"@en
"Ballinarry (Ogham Site)"@en
"Ballinrannig (Ogham Site)"@en
"Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)"@en

Simple view Ellipse Filter query results

geo

"nan""geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-7.468056 52.163056)""geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-10.176111 52.129444)""geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-9.330833 54.260278)""geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-7.047778 54.699444)""geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-10.138056 52.133056)""geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-8.846944 51.678889)""geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-10.063056 52.159167)""geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-10.061076 52.152143)""geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-9.733611 52.165556)""geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-9.772778 52.328889)""geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-7.729167 51.944167)""geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-10.049167 52.143056)""geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-9.662778 52.147778)""geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-10.236944 52.2675)""geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-9.088056 51.770833)""geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-10.2075 52.140556)""geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-8.377222 52.381944)""geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-10.386111 52.176111)""geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-10.031111 52.1725)""geo:wktLiteral

Dieses Projekt wird im Rahmen des Fellow-Programms Freies Wissen von Wikimedia Deutschland e.V. gefördert.

**FELLOW PROGRAMM
 FREIES WISSEN**
www.fellows.freieswissen.de

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N4O Knowledge Graph | <https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/sparql>

Wikidata & FactGrid

Erstellung von RDF aus Datenbank oder (Excel-)Listen

-

Open Refine / RDFier

Relationale Welt ... Daten mit Fremdschlüsseln verbunden. ... nicht wirklich lesbar!

coinfind

- id INT(11)
- Function_coin INT(11)
- FindSpot INT(11)
- Place INT(11)
- AdminDivision VARCHAR(21)
- Material INT(11)
- Mint INT(11)
- Mint2 INT(11)
- Period INT(11)
- Denomination INT(11)
- Denomination2 INT(11)
- FindCategory INT(11)
- CoinImage INT(11)
- CoinImage2 INT(11)
- DateFrom INT(11)
- DateTo INT(11)
- DateWritten VARCHAR(45)
- MintMark VARCHAR(45)
- Countermark VARCHAR(255)
- Weight DOUBLE
- DiameterMin DOUBLE
- DiameterMax DOUBLE
- DieAxis INT(11)
- ObverseReverse VARCHAR(700)
- FindCircumstances TEXT
- YearFound VARCHAR(100)
- OriginalSeen TINYINT(1)
- InternalNotes TEXT
- Cleaned TINYINT(1)
- Remarks TEXT

37 more...

Indexes

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
1	id	Function	FindSpot	Place	AdminDivision	Material	Mint	Mint2	Period	Denomination	Denomination2	FindCategory
2	5083	1	2315	135	DE_06_440_006		2	48	NULL	3	9	NULL
3	5271	1	2314	1601	DE_05_112_000		1	20	NULL	3	5	NULL
4	5273	1	2314	1601	DE_05_112_000		1	69	NULL	3	5	NULL
5	5274	1	2314	1601	DE_05_112_000		1	20	NULL	3	5	NULL
6	5275	1	2314	1601	DE_05_112_000		1	20	NULL	3	5	NULL
7	5276	1	2314	1601	DE_05_112_000		1	20	NULL	3	5	NULL
8	5277	1	2314	1601	DE_05_112_000		1	20	NULL	3	5	NULL
9	5278	1	2314	1601	DE_05_112_000		1	20	NULL	3	5	NULL
10	5279	1	2314	1601	DE_05_112_000		1	20	NULL	3	5	NULL
11	5280	1	2314	1601	DE_05_112_000		1	20	NULL	3	5	NULL
12	5281	1	2314	1601	DE_05_112_000		1	20	NULL	3	5	NULL
13	5282	1	2314	1601	DE_05_112_000		1	76	NULL	3	5	NULL

Primärschlüssel ist mit Tabellename innerhalb der Datenbank eindeutig!

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	id	Function	FindSpot	Place	AdminDivision	Material
2	5083	1	2315	135	DE_06_440_006	2
3	5271	1	2314	1601	DE_05_112_000	1
4	5273	1	2314	1601	DE_05_112_000	1
5	5274	1	2314	1601	DE_05_112_000	1
6	5275	1	2314	1601	DE_05_112_000	1
7	5276	1	2314	1601	DE_05_112_000	1
8	5277	1	2314	1601	DE_05_112_000	1
9	5278	1	2314	1601	DE_05_112_000	1
10	5279	1	2314	1601	DE_05_112_000	1
11	5280	1	2314	1601	DE_05_112_000	1
12	5281	1	2314	1601	DE_05_112_000	1
13	5282	1	2314	1601	DE_05_112_000	1

Tabelle: Material

	id	Name	Name_en	Description	Nomisma
▶	1	Gold	Gold		av
	2	Silber	Silver		ar
	3	Billon	Billon	Billon is any copper all...	billon
	4	Bronze	Bronze		ae
	6	Nickel	Nickel	Nickel is a common p...	ni
	7	Elektrum	Electrum	'EL' is the numismatic ...	el
	10	Blei	Lead	'PB' is the numismatic...	pb
	11	Unsicher	Uncertain		

Ist der eindeutige Nomisma Name im ID Namensraum:

ar → <https://nomisma.org/id/ar>

Diese URI ist eindeutig im WWW!

Views, um das zu erstellen, was wir verstehen ...

id	Material	Weight	MaxDiameter	FindPlace Name
289	Silber	1.6	16.7	Altkönig
5271	Gold	4.346	20.5	Großenbaum
5273	Gold	4.413	21.12	Großenbaum
5361	Bronze	26.14	28	Wotenitz (Lkr. Nordwestm...
5369	Gold	5.71	23	Muuks (Lkr. Vorpommern-...
6549	Gold	13.45	27	Ockritz (Lkr. Nordsachsen)
7911	Gold	7.02	19.83	Gommern (Lkr. Jerichowe...
8373	Gold	4.65	21	Deersheim (Lkr. Harz)
11469	Gold	3.59		
11028	Gold	4.5		

```
<nmo:NumismaticObject rdf:about="https://finds.org.uk/database/artefacts/record/id/1018642">
  <nmo:hasFindspot>
    <nmo:Find>
      <crm:P7_took_place_at>
        <crm:E53_Place>
          <rdfs:label xml:lang="en">Hollingbourne</rdfs:label>
          <crm:P89_falls_within rdf:resource="http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q9199209"/>
        </crm:E53_Place>
      </crm:P7_took_place_at>
    </nmo:Find>
  </nmo:hasFindspot>
</nmo:NumismaticObject>
```

```

<nmo:NumismaticObject rdf:about="https://finds.org.uk/database/artefacts/record/id/1018642">
  <nmo:hasFindspot>
    <nmo:Find>
      <crm:P7_took_place_at>
        <crm:E53_Place>
          <rdfs:label xml:lang="en">Hollingbourne</rdfs:label>
          <crm:P89_falls_within rdf:resource="http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q9199209"/>
        </crm:E53_Place>
      </crm:P7_took_place_at>
    </nmo:Find>
  </nmo:hasFindspot>
</nmo:NumismaticObject>

```

siehe auch: <https://nomisma.org/documentation/contribute/>

ID: 289

Bild AFE_9389_AFE_289_Altkönig.jpg

Herkunft: H. Junk

Lizenz: (c) H. Junk

nmo:hasFindspot

crm:P7_took_place_at

crm:P89_falls_within

geonames:2957069

Bild AFE_9389_AFE_289_Altkönig.jpg

Herkunft: H. Junk

Lizenz: (c) H. Junk

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1	id^^uri	nmo:hasFindspot^^blank**33	33_rdf:type^^uri	33_crm:P7_took_place_at^^blank**44	44_rdf:type^^uri	44_rdfs:label	44_crm:P89_falls_within^^uri
2	afe:289	2259	nmo:Find		34_crm:E53_Place	Altkönig	<https://sws.geonames.org/2957069>
3	afe:5271	2314	nmo:Find		1601_crm:E53_Place	Großenbaum	<https://sws.geonames.org/2951619>
4	afe:5273	2314	nmo:Find		1601_crm:E53_Place	Großenbaum	<https://sws.geonames.org/2951619>
5	afe:5361	783	nmo:Find		605_crm:E53_Place	Wotenitz (Lkr. Nordwestmecklenburg)	<https://sws.geonames.org/2806049>
6	afe:5369	790	nmo:Find		611_crm:E53_Place	Muuks (Lkr. Vorpommern-Rügen)	<https://sws.geonames.org/2867282>

```
namespaces.csv
1 prefix,namespace
2 crm,http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/
3 nm,http://nomisma.org/id/
4 nmo,http://nomisma.org/ontology#
5 rdf,http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#
6 rdfs,http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#
7 afe,http://afe.dainst.org/coin?afeid=
8
```

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	
1	id^^uri	nmo:hasMaterial^^uri	nmo:hasWeight	nmo:hasMaxDiameter	nmo:hasFindspot^^blank**33	33_rdf:type^^uri	33_crm:P7_took_place_at^^blank**44	44_rdf:type^^uri	44_rdfs:l
2	afe:289	<http://nomisma.org/id/ar>	1.6	16.7	2259	nmo:Find		34	crm:E53_Place
3	afe:5271	<http://nomisma.org/id/av>	4.34	20.5	2314	nmo:Find		1601	crm:E53_Place
4	afe:5273	<http://nomisma.org/id/av>	4.41	21.12	2314	nmo:Find		1601	crm:E53_Place
5	afe:5361	<http://nomisma.org/id/ae>	26.14		28	783	nmo:Find	605	crm:E53_Place
6	afe:5369	<http://nomisma.org/id/av>	5.71		23	790	nmo:Find	611	crm:E53_Place

Silber

RDFier <https://github.com/poepperl/rdfier>

MASTERTHESIS

Modellierung von Unsicherheiten in Daten:

Benchmarktests verschiedener Ansätze

zur Erlangung des akademischen Grades

Master of Science

vorgelegt von

Jan Luca Pöpperl

am 20.07.2023

https://github.com/UncertaintyC/unco/blob/main/master_thesis.pdf

Online unter: <https://rdfier.streamlit.app/>

Zzzz

This app has gone to sleep due to inactivity. Would you like to wake it back up?

Yes, get this app back up!

If you believe this is a bug, please [contact us](#) or visit the [Streamlit forums](#).

Namespaces

```
namespaces.csv
1 prefix,namespace
2 crm,http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/
3 nm,http://nomisma.org/id/
4 nmo,http://nomisma.org/ontology#
5 rdf,http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#
6 rdfs,http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#
7 afe,http://afe.dainst.org/coin?afeid=
```

The screenshot shows the RDFier application interface. The browser address bar displays `https://rdfier.streamlit.app`. The main content area features the title **RDFier** and subtitle **A RDF Mapper**. Below this, there are two upload sections: **Upload** and **Prefixes**. Each section contains a cloud icon, the text "Drag and drop file here", "Limit 200MB per file • CSV", and a "Browse files" button. A large blue arrow points from the "Namespaces" code block above to the "Prefixes" upload section. The left sidebar contains a menu with "RDFier", "How it works", and "Input Format".

RDFier

A RDF Mapper

Upload

Drag and drop file here

Limit 200MB per file • CSV

Browse files

Prefixes

Drag and drop file here

Limit 200MB per file • CSV

AFecoins_extraction_rdfier_find_top5.csv 0.9KB

namespaces.csv 245.0B

	id^uri	nmo:hasMaterial^uri	nmo:hasWeight	nmo:hasMaxDiameter	nmo:hasFindspot^blank**33	33_rdf:type^uri	33_crm:P7_took_place_at^blank**44	44_rdf:type^uri	44_rdfs:label
0	afe:289	<http://nomisma.org/id/ar>	1.6	16.7	2,259	nmo:Find	34	crm:E53_Place	Altkönig
1	afe:5271	<http://nomisma.org/id/av>	4.346	20.5	2,314	nmo:Find	1,601	crm:E53_Place	Großenbaum
2	afe:5273	<http://nomisma.org/id/av>	4.413	21.12	2,314	nmo:Find	1,601	crm:E53_Place	Großenbaum
3	afe:5361	<http://nomisma.org/id/ae>	26.14	28	783	nmo:Find	605	crm:E53_Place	Wotenitz (Lkr. Voigtl.)
4	afe:5369	<http://nomisma.org/id/av>	5.71	23	790	nmo:Find	611	crm:E53_Place	Muuk (Lkr. Voigtl.)

RDF Format

Turtle

XML

Generate RDF graph

```
@prefix afe: <http://afe.dainst.org/coin?afeid=> .
@prefix crm: <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/> .
@prefix nm: <http://nomisma.org/id/> .
@prefix nmo: <http://nomisma.org/ontology#> .
```

Show graph figure

Select model:

1: Transformation of RDF Reification

Namespaces:
 afe: <http://afe.dainst.org/coin?afeid=>
 crm: <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/>
 nm: <http://nomisma.org/id/>
 nmo: <http://nomisma.org/ontology#>
 rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
 xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>

Erstellt mit RDF-Grapher:
 requests.post(<https://www.ldf.fi/service/rdf-grapher>,
 ... aber auch manuell online möglich, gleiche URL.

Uncertainty

	id^^uri	nmo:hasMaterial^^uri**1	1__un:hasUncertainty^^certainty
0	afe:289	<http://nomisma.org/id/ar>	u
1	afe:5271	<http://nomisma.org/id/av>	None

Select model:

- 1: Transformation of RDF Reification
- 2: Integrating Uncertainty in RDF Statements
- 3: Assigning Reliability from CRM
- 4: Assigning Believability from CRMInf
- 5: Assigning .2-Properties from CRM
- 6: Adapting RDF Reification with EDTFO
- 7: Approximate Statements through EDTFO
- 8: Assigning Bundled Uncertainties
- 9a: RDF-star Approach

Namespaces:
 afe: <http://afe.dainst.org/coin?afeid=>
 nm: <http://nomisma.org/id/>
 nmo: <http://nomisma.org/ontology#>
 ns1: <http://www.w3.org/2005/Incubator/urw3/XGR-urw3-20080331/Uncertainty.owl#>
 rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>

Shortcut

?coin	?issuer
afe:4946	nm:antoninus_pius


```
select ?coin ?issuer where {
  ?coin nmo:hasIssuer ?issuer
}
```


?coin	?issuer
afe:4946	_b:1234

Openrefine <https://openrefine.org/>

human csv [Permalink](#)

50 rows

Show as: **rows** records Show: 5 **10** 25 50 100 500 1000 rows

All	id	Material	Weight	MaxDiameter	FindPlace Name	
☆	1.	289	Silber	1.6	16.7	Altkönig
☆	2.	5271	Gold			
☆	3.	5273	Gold			
☆	4.	5361	Bronze			
☆	5.	5369	Gold			
☆	6.	6549	Gold			
☆	7.	7911	Gold			
☆	8.	8373	Gold	4.65	21	DEUTSCHH (ENT. HAIZ)
☆	9.	11469	Gold	3.59	20	Arnstadt
☆	10.	11938	Gold	4.5	21	Leubingen

Data type: text

Apply **Apply to all identical cells** **Cancel**

Enter Ctrl-Enter Esc

id	Material	Weight
289	Silber	1.6
5271	https://nomisma.org/id/av	4.346
5273	https://nomisma.org/id/av	4.413
5361	Bronze	26.14
5369	https://nomisma.org/id/av	5.71
6549	https://nomisma.org/id/av	13.45
7911	https://nomisma.org/id/av	7.02
8373	https://nomisma.org/id/av	4.65
11469	https://nomisma.org/id/av	3.59
11938	https://nomisma.org/id/av	4.5

Nomisma.org OpenRefine Reconciliation Service

Service URI: <http://nomisma.org/apis/reconcile>

Wikidata

Wikidata ...

What is Wikidata?

- ✦ **A free and open knowledge base and data hub**
→ everybody can add and edit
- ✦ central storage for structured data of **Wikimedia** projects

data in **Wikidata** is:

- ✦ **available** under a free license (CC 0)
- ✦ **multilingual**
- ✦ **accessible** to humans and machines (GUI & API & SPARQL)
- ✦ **exportable** using standard formats (JSON, RDF, XML)
- ✦ **interlinked** to other open data sets on the LOD Cloud

Wikidata and the LOD Cloud

data local (offline)

data online

data online & open

data part of LOD

Wikidata in the Linked Open Data Cloud

Linked Data & Wikidata in archaeology

via 10.3390/digital2030019

The screenshot shows the MDPI Digital journal article page. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the MDPI logo, links for Journals, Topics, Information, Author Services, Initiatives, and About, and buttons for Sign In / Sign Up and Submit. Below this is a search bar with fields for Title / Keyword, Author / Affiliation / Email, Digital, and All Article Types, along with Search and Advanced buttons. The breadcrumb trail reads: Journals / Digital / Volume 2 / Issue 3 / 10.3390/digital2030019.

The article page features a left sidebar with the journal logo, submission and review buttons, and an Article Menu. The menu includes Academic Editors (Markos Katsianis, Tuna Kalayci, Apostolos Sarris), Subscribe SciFeed, Recommended Articles, Related Info Link, and More by Authors Links. At the bottom of the sidebar, it shows Article Views (5726) and Citations (7).

The main content area displays the article title "Practices of Linked Open Data in Archaeology and Their Realisation in Wikidata" by Sophie C. Schmidt, Florian Thiery, and Martina Trognitz. It includes the authors' affiliations, a list of footnotes, the article's DOI, submission and publication dates, and buttons for Download, Browse Figures, Review Reports, and Versions Notes. The abstract discusses the use of Linked Open Data (LOD) in archaeology to connect dispersed data sources and enable cross-querying, highlighting the role of Wikidata as an open knowledge hub. The keywords are linked open data, Wikidata, and archaeology.

On the right side of the article, there is a vertical toolbar with icons for Altmetric, Share, Help, Cite, Discuss in SciProfiles, Endorse, and Comment.

Linked Data in Wikidata: An example

Olaf Tausch, CC BY 3.0, via Wikimedia Commons

<https://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q465338>

<https://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q249707>

<https://www.wikidata.org/entity/P189>

Grafiken: Martina Trognitz, CC BY 4.0, via 10.3390/digital2030019

Linked Data in Wikidata: An example

Grafiken: Martina Trognitz, CC BY 4.0, via 10.3390/digital2030019

Wikibase & Wikidata Datamodel

- ❖ **Items**
 - Label
 - Description
 - Alias
 - Identifier

- ❖ **Statements**
 - Property
 - Value
 - Qualifier
 - Reference

MTrognitz, LLC, via Wikimedia Commons

Phaistos disc (Q465338)

WIKIDATA

- Main page
- Community portal
- Project chat
- Create a new Item
- Recent changes
- Random Item
- Query Service
- Nearby
- Help
- Donate

Lexicographical data

- Create a new Lexeme
- Recent changes
- Random Lexeme

Tools

- What links here
- Related changes
- Special pages
- Permanent link
- Page information
- Concept URI
- Cite this page
- Get shortened URL
- Download QR code

Item [Discussion](#)

Phaistos disc (Q465338)

inscribed tablet found in Crete with undeciphered spiral scriptures [edit](#)

Phaistos Disk | Phaestos Disc

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Phaistos disc	inscribed tablet found in Crete with undeciphered spiral scriptures	Phaistos Disk Phaestos Disc
German	Diskos von Phaistos	Tonscheibe aus der Bronzezeit	Diskos von Festós Diskos von Phaistós Phaistos Phaistos-Scheibe Diskos von Festos
Italian	disco di Festo	disco di terracotta rinvenuto nell'isola di Creta	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	

All entered languages

Statements

instance of	<div>clay tablet edit</div> <div>► 1 reference</div>
	<div>archaeological artifact edit</div> <div>▼ 0 references</div>

[+ add reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

Phaistos disc (Q465338)

inception	17. century BCE	
	▶ 1 reference	
	1850 BCE	
	earliest date 1850 BCE latest date 1600 BCE sourcing circumstances circa	
▶ 1 reference		
1400 BCE		
latest date 1301 BCE sourcing circumstances after		
▶ 1 reference		
1700 BCE		
earliest date 1700 BCE latest date 1100 BCE sourcing circumstances circa reason for preferred rank preferred determination method		
▼ 1 reference		
author Louis Godart page(s) 206 stated in Le pouvoir de l'écrit		
+ add reference		
1400 BCE		
earliest date 1400 BCE latest date 1340 BCE sourcing circumstances circa		
▶ 1 reference		
+ add value		

country	Greece	
	▼ 0 references	
	+ add reference	
	Ancient Crete	
▼ 0 references		
+ add reference		
Minoan civilization		
▼ 0 references		
+ add reference		
+ add value		
located in the administrative territorial entity	Heraklion Prefecture	
	▼ 0 references	
+ add reference		
+ add value		
location	Heraklion Archaeological Museum	
	▶ 1 reference	
+ add value		
coordinate location		
	35°3'6.05"N, 24°48'53.60"E	
	▼ 1 reference	
	imported from Wikimedia project	Catalan Wikipedia
+ add reference		
+ add value		

via <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q465338>

Wikidata SPARQL Query: Archäologische Artefakte

Wikidata Query Service

Examples Help More tools

1 (Input a SPARQL query or choose a query example)

?

w.wiki/BFXq

query.wikidata.org

Wikidata SPARQL Query: Archäologische Artefakte

Wikidata SPARQL Query: Archäologische Artefakte

Wikidata SPARQL Query: Archäologische Artefakte

Boundary stone with eagle (Q17445038)

 WIKIDATA

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Get shortened URL
Download QR code

Item: [Discussion](#)

Boundary stone with eagle (Q17445038)

monument in Vaals, Netherlands

[In more languages](#)
Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Boundary stone with eagle	monument in Vaals, Netherlands	
German	Adlerstein Grenzstein (Aachen)	Vaals, Netherlands	Adlerstein am Vaalser Berg („Sc...
Italian	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	

All entered languages

Statements

instance of

-
- 0 references
-
- 0 references
-
- 0 references

image

Vaals-Grenssteen achter Wilhelmintoren (1).JPG
3,000 x 4,000; 4.11 MB
point in time 22 November 2010

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

Ogham!

R.A.S. Macalister, *Corpus inscriptionum insularum Celticarum*, vol. I (1945) / p.502

A		M		H		B	
O		G		D		L	
U		NG		T		V	
E		Z		C		S	
I		R		Q		N	

Al-qamar, CC BY-SA 3.0, via Wikimedia Commons

CIIC 197. Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

The Open Ogham Data Workflow!

Florian Thiery, Timo Homburg, Sophie C. Schmidt und Martina Trognitz, CC BY 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

SPARQL Query: Ogham in Wikidata

query.wikidata.org

SPARQL Query: Ogham in Wikidata

```
SELECT ?item ?itemLabel ?geo ?img WHERE {
  ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q2016147.
  OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P625 ?geo. }
  OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P18 ?img. }
  SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
}
```


Wikidata WikiProject Ogham Stones

[English](#) [Fñhiygeeo](#) [🗺️](#) [Talk](#) [Preferences](#) [Beta](#) [Watchlist](#) [Contributions](#) [Log out](#)

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Page information
Get shortened URL
Download QR code

In Wikipedia [Add links](#)

Wikidata:WikiProject OghamStones

- Wikidata Entry: [WikiProject OghamStones \(Q128491028\)](#) supported by the [Research Squirrel Engineers Network \(Q73901970\)](#)
- Commons Category: [Category:Ogham stones](#)

Contents [hide]

- Statements to model an Ogham Stone in an exhibition
- Examples
 - Ogham Stones in the Cork Public Museum
 - Ogham Stones at the UCC Stone Corridor
 - Ogham Stones at Trinity College, Dublin
 - Ogham Stones at the National Museum, Dublin
 - Ogham Stones at Músaem Chorca Dhulibhne
- Statements to model an Ogham Stone in the wild
- Examples
 - Ogham Stones in the Co. Kerry
 - TODO
- Contributors

Statements to model an Ogham Stone in an exhibition [edit]

Property	Example	description
Statements		
instance of (P31)	ogham stone (Q2016147) Ogham Stone Semantic Concept (Q106502643) archaeological artifact (Q220659)	defines it as an Ogham Stone, archaeological artefact and Ogham Stone Semantic Concept
part of (P361)	WikiProject OghamStones (Q128491028) Ogham Stone Semantic Concept (Q106502643)	part of WikiProjects and a semantic concept
image (P18)	divers	Wikimedia Commons image, if multiple add <i>pref. rank</i> (optional)
country (P17)	divers	country, e.g. Ireland (Q27)
located in the administrative territorial entity (P131)	divers	county, e.g. County Cork (Q162475)
location (P276)	divers	museum + exhibition, e.g. University College Cork (Q1574185) + UCC Stone Corridor (Q121592049)
coordinate location (P525)	WGS84	using qualifier location (P275) <i>ex situ</i> (Q1383330), sourcing circumstances (P1480) <i>on-site survey</i> (Q120965429), determination method (P459) <i>on-site survey</i> (Q120965429), subject has role (P2868) exhibition (Q484680) , stated in (P248) OpenStreetMap (Q698) , reference OpenStreetMap node ID (P11993) , add <i>pref. rank</i>
creator (P170)	Ogham Person Concept (Q110897921)	Ogham Person as creator (only needed if <i>non-free artwork image URL (P6500)</i> is used)
collection (P109)	divers	collection, e.g. Stone Corridor University College Cork (Q59379477)
inventory number (P217)	divers	inventory number of the collection, set a <i>pref. rank</i>
location of discovery (P189)	divers	ogham site, e.g. Barrahaunin (Ogham Site) (Q59379412)
external data available at URL (P1325)	URL	ref. to 3D-model in Sketchfab , using qualifier object of statement has role (P3831) 3D model (Q3889833) , publisher (P123) , published in (P1433) , copyright license (P275) , add <i>pref. rank</i>
inscription (P1584)	latin	inscription, e.g. C[A]RRTTACC MMAQI MOU CAGG (Latin)
state of conservation (P5816)	divers	status, e.g. partially destroyed (Q30539160) (optional)
non-free artwork image URL (P6500)	divers	external image (optional), using qualifier copyright license (P275) , publisher (P123) , object of statement has role (P3831)
partially coincident with (P1382)	divers	other concepts, e.g., BARHA/1 (Ogham Stone Concept by CISP) (Q108675359) , CIIC 103 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister) (Q59377850)
Identifiers		
OpenStreetMap node ID (P11993)	divers	Open Street Map Node

Wikidata SPARQL Query: Archäologische Artefakte

Ogham Stone Coumeenole North / Dunmore Head, Co. Kerry (Q126503090)

 WIKIDATA

Item [Discussion](#)

Ogham Stone Coumeenole North / Dunmore Head, Co. Kerry (Q126503090)

Ogham Stone, Co. Kerry edit
Coumeenole Stone

[In more languages](#)

Statements

instance of	
	0 references + add reference
	
	0 references + add reference
	
	0 references + add reference
	+ add value

part of	
	0 references + add reference
	
	0 references + add reference
	+ add value

image	
-------	---

[Coumeenole Ogham Stone \(Dunmore Head\).jpg](#)
960 × 1,280; 122 KB

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

Ogham Stone CIIC 81 at UCC Cork

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- Donate

- Lexicographical data
- Create a new Lexeme
- Recent changes
- Random Lexeme

- Tools
- What links here
- Related changes
- Special pages
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- Get shortened URL
- Download QR code

Item [Discussion](#)

81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project) (Q106)

Ogham Stone, Ireland [edit](#)

[In more languages](#)

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project)	Ogham Stone, Ireland	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Italian	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	

All entered languages

Statements

instance of	ogham stone 0 references
	Ogham Stone Concept 0 references
	Ogham Stone Semantic Concept 0 references

inscription mentions	MAQI object of statement has role 0 references	Ogham Formula Word
	MUCOI object of statement has role 0 references	Ogham Formula Word
	cassittas (Ogham Person) object of statement has role 0 references	Ogham Nomenclature Word
	calliti (Ogham Person) object of statement has role 0 references	Ogham Nomenclature Word
inscription	C[A]SSITT[A]S MAQI MUCOI CALLITI (Irish)	

Florian Thiery, CC BY-SA 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

Identifiers

Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID	CO074-148---- 0 references
OpenStreetMap node ID	11071361392 0 references

CIIC 81 → Found in Garranes (Lisheenagreine)

Item [Discussion](#)

81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project) (Q106680733)

Ogham Stone, Ireland

[In more languages](#)

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project)	Ogham Stone, Ireland	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	
Polish	No label defined	No description defined	

Statements

instance of	 ogham stone edit
	0 references
	+ add reference
 Ogham Stone Concept edit	0 references
	+ add reference
	 Ogham Stone Concept (Research Squirrel Ogham Project) edit
	0 references
	+ add reference
	+ add value

via <https://www.jstor.org/stable/25505959>

51°48′59.58″N, 8°45′57.13″W

- determination method [georeferencing](#)
- object has role [book entry \(Ogham\)](#)
- subject has role [archaeological site](#)
- stated in [academic journal article](#)

[1 reference](#)

- reference URL <https://www.corkhist.ie/wp-content/uploads/jfiles/1931/b1931-020.pdf>
- <https://www.jstor.org/stable/25505959>

CIIC 81 → currently at UCC Cork #4

Item [Discussion](#)

81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project) (Q106680733)

Ogham Stone, Ireland

[In more languages](#)
Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project)	Ogham Stone, Ireland	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	
Polish	No label defined	No description defined	

Statements

instance of	ogham stone
	▼ 0 references
	Ogham Stone Concept
	▼ 0 references
Ogham Stone Concept (Research Squirrel Ogham Project)	
	▼ 0 references

Florian Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

51°53'37.7254"N, 8°29'31.6313"W

location ex situ
 sourcing circumstances on-site survey
 determination method on-site survey
 subject has role exhibition
 stated in OpenStreetMap

▼ 1 reference

OpenStreetMap node ID 11071361392

ChatGPT und Wikidata auf arabisch...

استعلام SPARQL من فضلك على Wikidata، مع جميع نقاط البحث Samian (Q102202066) والإحداثيات

للحصول على نقاط البحث للإحداثيات المتعلقة بـ "Samian" (Q102202066) من ويكي بيانات باستخدام SPARQL، يمكنك استخدام الاستعلام التالي:

```
Code kopieren
```

```
SELECT ?item ?itemLabel ?coordinate
WHERE {
  ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q102202066; # نقطة البحث Samian
        wdt:P625 ?coordinate. # الإحداثيات
  SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
}
```

شرح الاستعلام:

- `?item`: يمثل عنصر نقطة البحث.
- `?itemLabel`: يعيد اسم نقطة البحث.
- `?coordinate`: يمثل الإحداثيات لنقطة البحث.
- `wdt:P31`: يمثل خاصية "نوع العنصر".
- `wd:Q102202066`: هو معرف Samian في ويكي بيانات.
- `wdt:P625`: يمثل خاصية "الإحداثيات".

يمكنك استخدام هذا الاستعلام على Wikidata Query Service للحصول على النتائج.

Sende eine Nachricht an ChatGPT

<https://w.wiki/BHyW>

<https://chatgpt.com/share/66f32c9c-12d8-800d-81d1-52e162bcfd03>

```
Wikidata Query Service
```

```
1 SELECT ?item ?itemLabel ?coordinate
2 WHERE {
3   ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q102202066. # Finds all instances of Samian (Q102202066)
4   ?item wdt:P625 ?coordinate. # Retrieves the coordinates (P625)
5   SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
6 }
```


... und English ...

To retrieve search points with coordinates related to "Samian" (Q102202066) from Wikidata using SPARQL, you can use the following query:

```
sparql Code kopieren  
  
SELECT ?item ?itemLabel ?coordinate  
WHERE {  
  ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q102202066; # Samian search point  
        wdt:P625 ?coordinate. # coordinates  
  SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }  
}
```

Query Explanation:

- `?item` : Represents the search point item.
- `?itemLabel` : Returns the name (label) of the search point.
- `?coordinate` : Represents the coordinates of the search point.
- `wdt:P31` : Represents the "instance of" property.
- `wd:Q102202066` : The identifier for "Samian" on Wikidata.
- `wdt:P625` : Represents the "coordinates" property.

You can run this query on the [Wikidata Query Service](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata_Query_Service) to get the results.

<https://w.wiki/BHyW>

<https://chatgpt.com/share/66f32c9c-12d8-800d-81d1-52e162bcfd03>

The screenshot shows the Wikidata Query Service interface. At the top, there are navigation links for 'Examples', 'Help', 'More tools', and 'Query Builder'. Below this, a SPARQL query is displayed in a text area, with line numbers 1 through 6. The query is: `1 SELECT ?item ?itemLabel ?coordinate`, `2 WHERE {`, `3 ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q102202066. # Finds all instances of Samian (Q102202066)`, `4 ?item wdt:P625 ?coordinate. # Retrieves the coordinates (P625)`, `5 SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }`, `6 }`. To the left of the query area are several icons: an information icon, a crosshair icon, a pin icon, and a diamond icon.

Hands On: Wikidata

<https://github.com/Research-Squirrel-Engineers/workshop-n4ocm24-mainz>

<https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/workshop-n4ocm24-mainz/>

Example: Archaeological Sites in RLP as Map with images

Wikidata Query Service [Beispiele](#) [Hilfe](#) [Weitere Werkzeuge](#) [Abfragegenerator](#)

Abfragehelfer

+ Filter

- ist ein(e) beliebiges archäologische Stätte
- Unterklasse von
- Staat Deutschland
- liegt in der Verwaltungseinheit Rheinland-Pfalz

+ Anzeigen

- geographische Koordinaten
- Bild

Begrenzung

```
1 #Archaeological Sites in Rhineland-Palatinate (Germany)
2 #defaultView:Map
3 SELECT DISTINCT ?item ?itemLabel ?geo ?img WHERE {
4   ?item (wdt:P31/(wdt:P279*)) wd:Q839954.
5   ?item wdt:P17 wd:Q183.
6   ?item wdt:P131 wd:Q1200.
7   ?item wdt:P625 ?geo.
8   OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P18 ?img }
9   SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
10 }
```

Example: Archaeological Sites in RLP as Map with images

Römersteine im Zahlbachtal (Q896423)

- Main page
- Community portal
- Project chat
- Create a new item
- Recent changes
- Random item
- Query Service
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- Get shortened URL
- Download QR code

Item [Discussion](#)

Restant aquaduct van Mogontiacum (Q896423)

archaeological site in Rhineland-Palatinate, Germany [edit](#)

→ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Restant aquaduct van Mogontiacum	archaeological site in Rhineland-Palatinate, Germany	
German	Römersteine im Zahlbachtal	archäologische Stätte in Deutschland	
Italian	Acquedotto di Mogontiacum	No description defined	Acquedotto di Magonza
American English	No label defined	No description defined	

All entered languages

Statements

instance of	archaeological site edit
	1 reference

image

Römersteine.jpg
400 × 267; 100 KB

1 reference

Römersteine 05.JPG
3,264 × 2,448; 1.24 MB

Nixnubix, CC BY 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

Example: Caves with prehistoric art as Map with images

Example: Limes castrum (Roman fortification)

Example: Samian Ware Findspots

Example: Samian Ware Kiln Sites

Example: Samian Ware Kiln Regions

Example: Ogham Stone Sites (Irish Provinces)

Example: Ogham Stone Sites (Dingle Peninsula)

Example: Ogham Stone Sites (Dingle Peninsula, “MAQI”)

Example: Holy Wells in Ireland (and named after)

Hands On: FactGrid

<https://github.com/Research-Squirrel-Engineers/workshop-n4ocm24-mainz>

<https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/workshop-n4ocm24-mainz/>

FactGrid - a database for historians

The screenshot shows the main page of the FactGrid database. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for 'Main Page', 'Discussion', 'Read', 'View source', and 'View history'. A search bar is located on the right side of the navigation bar. The main content area is titled 'Main Page' and features a 'Welcome!' message. The message includes a list of flags representing the project's multilingual nature and a paragraph explaining the database's purpose and how to use it. A sidebar on the left contains various links for navigation and search. On the right side, there are two sections: 'Jour fixe' and 'Message Board'. The 'Jour fixe' section contains an announcement about a weekly meeting. The 'Message Board' section contains a note about a security feature in the QuickStatements version.

English Log in

Main Page Discussion

Read View source View history Search FactGrid

Main Page

🇩🇪 🇪🇸 🇫🇷 🇮🇹 🇵🇹 🇷🇺 🇹🇷

Welcome!

to the FactGrid database, a project of the Gotha Research Centre operated by the data lab of the University of Erfurt. With the support of Wikimedia Germany we are using a MediaWiki with Wikidata's "wikibase" extension. Our main product are data which we collect on "Items" such as these:

- Adam Weishaupt
- Paris

You will need to be logged in to see the "add statement" link with which you can add information in the form of triple based machine readable claims — which everyone can now explore with the SPARQL data mining language, at our [Query Service](#). All FactGrid data are CC0-licensed. You can download any search in various data formats with the aim to explore FactGrid data in other software environments or visualise searches with various tools on our site.

Visit our

- [FactGrid FAQ](#) for more information on why you might love to use FactGrid as your research platform
- [Help Section](#) for further assistance
- [Terms of Service](#) if you want to have an account on FactGrid
- [Project Section](#) to take a look at work done on the collective platform

The FactGrid database is an open collaborative and multilingual project organised by — as of August 2024 — [445 participants](#) / by [language](#) / by [gender](#) from all over the world. If you are looking for a site to present research data and keep them in the process of further research — the FactGrid database might be a cool candidate. For more information and account details contact:

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99867 Gotha
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mobile: +49-179-5196880
olaf.simons@pierre-marteau.com

<https://database.factgrid.de/wiki/Hauptseite>

Jour fixe

It has been proposed to have a weekly jour fixe on Thursdays 21:30 CET (a time equally (in)convenient to all our teams around the world). FactGrid has an open web channel for such purposes that can be used without further passwords and software downloads. Contact olaf.simons@pierre-marteau.com for link details.

QuickStatements

Note that the new QuickStatements Version has an annoying security feature implemented on regular user accounts: If you press "Run" you will receive loads of errors after the 90th edit. To avoid this you must use the "Run in background" option.

We hope we can get this obstacle removed, but for the time being we run the platform with Wikidata-settings. —Olaf Simons (talk) 12:24, 13 March 2023 (CET)

Message Board

Sample Queries & FactGrid Query Service

- Main page
- Query service
- Sample queries
- Advanced text search
- Recent changes
- Browse
 - FactGrid Viewer
 - KnoBase Browser
 - EntiTree genealogies
- Project Spaces
- Blog
 - Projects historically
 - Projects alphabetically
 - Projects personally
- To Do
- SPARQL Lab
- Items & Properties
 - New Item
 - Mergelitems
 - Batch fragments
 - QuickStatements
 - Directory of Properties
 - New Property
 - Data modeling
- Help
- Lexemes
 - New Lexeme
 - Search
- Tools

Project page **Discussion** Read View source View history Search FactGrid

FactGrid:Sample queries

- Help:
- https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:SPARQL_query_service/Wikidata_Query_Help/Result_VIEWS/en
 - <https://en.wikibooks.org/wiki/SPARQL/FILTER>

Contents [hide]

- Looking for people
- Looking for documents
- Looking for dates
- Maps
 - 4.1 Dots
 - 4.2 Lines
- Tables
- Graphs
- Timelines
- Statistics
 - 8.1 Prevent double listings
- Grammatically intricate searches
 - 9.1 Wikimedia sources
 - 9.2 Statements with sources
 - 9.3 Statements with unit information
 - 9.4 Get information from connected items
 - 9.5 Search for specific Qualifiers on a Statement
 - 9.6 Search for all the Qualifiers on Statements with the same property
 - 9.7 You already know one related value
 - 9.8 Looking for a statement - give it with all the qualifying statements
- Missing Statements
- Missing connections
- Wildcards
- State all statements that are made on an item

https://database.factgrid.de/wiki/FactGrid:Sample_queries

The screenshot shows the FactGrid Query interface. At the top, there are navigation options: 'Beispiele', 'Hilfe', and 'Weitere Werkzeuge'. The main area contains a text input field with the placeholder text '(Eine SPARQL-Abfrage eingeben oder eine Beispielabfrage auswählen)'. Below the input field, there is a map view showing a geographical area with a red location marker. The interface is in German, as indicated by the 'Deutsch' language selector in the top right corner.

<https://database.factgrid.de/query/>

Pharmacies in Koblenz (Mapping Koblenz Project)

Hands On: SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

<https://github.com/Research-Squirrel-Engineers/workshop-n4ocm24-mainz>

<https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/workshop-n4ocm24-mainz/>

Die SPARQL Unicorn Idee

What is the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin?

There is a lack of
FLOSS GIS tools
for **Linked Open Data**.

The **SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin** addresses the problem of the lack of availability of tools for Semantic Web geodata.

<https://github.com/sparqlunicorn/sparqlunicornGoesGIS>
via 10.5281/zenodo.3786814

What is the SPARQL Unicorn?

The **SPARQL Unicorn** allows the *execution of Linked Data queries* in (Geo)SPARQL to selected triplestores and geo-enabled SPARQL endpoints and thus prepares the results of the queries in QGIS for the geocommunity.^{oqgis}

<https://github.com/sparqlunicorn/sparqlunicornGoesGIS>
via 10.5281/zenodo.3786814

What is the SPARQL Unicorn?

The **SPARQL Unicorn** allows the *Transformation from CSV or GeoJSON into RDF* (e.g. GeoSPARQL).

<https://github.com/sparqlunicorn/sparqlunicornGoesGIS>
via 10.5281/zenodo.3786814

What is the SPARQL Unicorn?

The **SPARQL Unicorn**
allows a *RDF*
HTML-Documentation.

<https://github.com/sparqlunicorn/sparqlunicornGoesGIS>
via 10.5281/zenodo.3786814

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin Download

Version 0.17

Nutzt das jemand?

Nutzt das jemand?

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Bringing Federated Semantic Queries to the GIS-Based Scenario

by Oswaldo Páez 1 and Luis M. Vilches-Blázquez 2,*

Luis M. Vilches-Blázquez [Scopus](#) [ORCID](#) [Preprints.org](#) [Google Scholar](#)

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THE INTEGRATION OF SEMANTIC NETWORKS IN VIRTUAL EXHIBITIONS

B. Danthine, G. Hiebel, C. Posch, and H. Stadler

Keywords: CIDOC CRM, Semantic Network, 3D, GIS, Virtual Reality, Case Study

Abstract. In this article a use case is presented how a semantic network can be used to enrich the existing virtual exhibition "They Shared their Destiny: Women and the Cossacks' Tragedy in Lienz 1945" about the fate of women during the Cossack tragedy in Lienz. By connecting via CIDOC CRM information about people, events, finds and places the goal was not only to make this information interoperable, but also to integrate the resulting knowledge graph into the exhibition, thus providing a further navigation level and enhancing the visitors' experience.

First, a short introduction to the existing exhibition and the presented project is given. In the second part, the scientific background of CIDOC CRM and its semantically enriched 3D content is outlined. In the third part the implementation and the project as a use case is described with respect to the data modelling and the integration of the semantic network into the 3-dimensional environment as well as the integration of spatial aspects and other internet resources. At the end, there is a summary with an outlook on future planned projects.

How to cite: Danthine, B., Hiebel, G., Posch, C., and Stadler, H.: THE INTEGRATION OF SEMANTIC NETWORKS IN VIRTUAL EXHIBITIONS, Int. Arch. Photogramm. Remote Sens. Spatial Inf. Sci., XLVI-M-1-2021, 165–172, <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLVI-M-1-2021-165-2021>, 2021.

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Methodology for the incorporation of geographic information in Wikidata

Ángel Obregón-Sierra
Universidad Isabel I

Javier López-Otero
Universidad Isabel I

Antonio Gavira-Narváez
Universidad Isabel I

Rafael F. Vega-Pozuelo
Universidad Isabel I

Palabras clave: Wikidata, Open data, SPARQL, GIS, Spatial analysis, Triangulation station

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UNIVERSIDAD DE SEVILLA

77 CALIDAD INVESTIGACIÓN

SPARQL-Queries

Wikidata Queries in QGIS (here: Holy Wells)

The screenshot shows the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin interface. At the top, there are tabs for 'Abfragen', 'Interlinken', and 'Anreicherung (Experimentell)'. The 'Endpoint auswählen:' dropdown is set to 'Wikidata --> ?item ?geo [SPARQL Endpoint]'. The 'Queryvorlagen:' dropdown is set to 'Item+Label', and the 'Layer Name:' is 'holy_wells'. The main area contains a SPARQL query:

```
1 SELECT DISTINCT ?item ?itemLabel ?img ?geo ?osm ?namedafterLabel WHERE {  
2   ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q1371047, wd:Q126443332.  
3   OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P18 ?img. }  
4   OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P625 ?geo. }  
5   OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P11693 ?osm. }  
6   OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P138 ?namedafter. }  
7   SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "en". }  
8 }
```

On the right side, there is a list of 'GeoConcepts (500)' with various results, including 'Antarctic field camp (wd:Q4771007)', 'Bahá'í temple (wd:Q1568313)', 'British overseas territories (wd:Q46395)', 'Catholic cathedral (wd:Q56242215)', 'Centaur (wd:Q761888)', 'Chondrocladia concrescens (wd:Q1828566)', 'Christian denomination (wd:Q879146)', 'Christian school (wd:Q867738)', 'Coche (wd:Q5403750)', 'Conservatory of departmental relevance ...', 'Ecclesiastical circumscription immediately ...', 'French overseas collectivity (wd:Q719487)', 'French wine (wd:Q630531)', 'Gendarmerie barracks (wd:Q83554028)', 'Gregorian telescope (wd:Q742318)', 'Mars crater (wd:Q1475691)', 'Mercury crater (wd:Q76833930)', 'NOAA Weather Radio station ...', 'National Monument of the United States ...', 'National Park of the United States ...', 'National Reserve (wd:Q6978070)', 'National Wildlife Refuge (wd:Q1410668)', 'One Earth Ecoregion (wd:Q124221947)', 'Plinian eruption (wd:Q747501)', 'Protestant church building (wd:Q56242063)', 'Roman Catholic metropolitan archdiocese ...', 'S-42 (wd:Q1887138)', 'Scenic Reserve (wd:Q63248569)', 'Sekolah Menengah Atas (wd:Q97598588)', 'Sekolah Menengah Pertama (wd:Q97500812)', and 'Surtseyan eruption (wd:Q1060842)'. At the bottom, there are buttons for 'Gespeicherte Queries: ChristSch', 'Query laden', 'Queryname:', and 'Query speichern', along with a 'Layer hinzufügen' button and a 'Language for query results: English (en)' dropdown.

Wikidata Queries in QGIS (here: Holy Wells)

Wikidata Queries in QGIS (here: Holy Wells)

id	img	itemLabel	namedafterLabel	osm	
109	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126923120	NULL	Kilmog Holy Well	friar	NULL
110	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126919273	NULL	Friar's Well	friar	NULL
111	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126491170	NULL	Q126491170	head	NULL
112	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126454486	NULL	Well of the head	head	8515246136
113	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126454486	NULL	Well of the head	headache	8515246136
114	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126655791	NULL	Caereeachth Well	herd	NULL
115	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126472909	NULL	Trinity Well	Holy Trinity	NULL
116	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126374490	http://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Trinity Well.jpg	Trinity Well	Holy Trinity	11942593399
117	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126438084	NULL	Holy Trinity Well	Holy Trinity	8517739108
118	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126486274	http://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:John's Well.jpg	John's Well	John the Baptist	8539018118
119	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126474774	http://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:St John's Well.jpg	St John's Well	John the Baptist	8567014803
120	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126456561	NULL	St. John's Well	John the Baptist	6535302216
121	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126472933	http://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:St James's Well.jpg	St. James's Well	Kings River	8522332218
122	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q121840779	http://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:St. Lachtain's Well (Toberlactain).jpg	St. Lachtain's Well (Toberlactain)	Lachtin mac Tarbín	NULL
123	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q127048193	NULL	Saint Laurence's Well	Lawrence of Rome	NULL
124	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126454422	http://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:St Leonard's Well.jpg	St Leonard's Well	Leonard of Noblac	7412516778
125	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126949808	NULL	Loughman's Well	Loughman	NULL
126	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q122303936	NULL	Saint Luke's Well	Luke	8526425065
127	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126478503	NULL	St. Mocuille's Well	Mac Cuill	8522349432
128	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126454603	http://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:St Mogue's Well.jpg	St. Mogue's Well	Máedóc of Ferns	7995685476
129	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126485951	NULL	St. Margaret's Well	Margaret the Virgin	8515639045
130	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126476522	NULL	St. Martin's Well	Martin of Tours	8490582674
131	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126890179	NULL	St. Mary's Well	Mary	NULL
132	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q12646306	NULL	Lady's Well	Mary	NULL
133	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126645328	NULL	Q126645328	Mary	NULL
134	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q12688828	NULL	Lady's Well	Mary	NULL
135	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126617074	NULL	Our Lady's Well	Mary	NULL
136	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126499565	NULL	Tobar Muire	Mary	11973631439
137	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126478980	NULL	Lady's Well	Mary	NULL

FactGrid Queries in QGIS (here: Buildings in Koblenz)

The screenshot shows the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin interface. The main window is titled "SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin" and has a menu bar with "Linked Data Processing", "Queryhelfer", "Einstellungen", and "Hilfe". Below the menu bar are three tabs: "Abfragen", "Interlinken", and "Anreicherung (Experimentell)".

The "Abfragen" tab is active. It contains the following fields and controls:

- Endpoint auswählen:** A dropdown menu showing "Factgrid --> ?item ?geo [SPARQL Endpoint]" and a "Quick Add RDF Resource" button.
- Filter Concept Results:** An empty text input field.
- Queryvorlagen:** A dropdown menu showing "Item+Label".
- Layer Name:** A text input field containing "buildings".

The main area is a text editor with a "Valid Query" label. It contains the following SPARQL query:

```
1 SELECT ?item ?itemLabel ?geo ?layerLabel WHERE {  
2 ?item wdt:P131 wd:Q922978.  
3 ?item wdt:P2 ?layer.  
4 ?item wdt:P48 ?geo.  
5 SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "en". }  
6 } ORDER BY ?typeLabel
```

At the bottom of the text editor, there are buttons for "Gespeicherte Queries:", "Query laden", "Queryname:", and "Query speichern". Below these is a "Layer hinzufügen" button.

On the right side of the interface, there is a list of "GeoConcepts (293)". The list includes various categories such as "Abandoned village", "Abbey", "Academic Gymnasium", "Academy for young noblemen", "Academy of sciences", "Administrative district", "Administrative quarter in Paris", "Aid agency", "Amt", "Ancient settlement", "Archipelago", "Architectural structure", "Archive", "Arrondissement of Paris", "Art museum", "Art school", "Association", "Astronomical observatory", "Autonomous community of Spain", "Barony", "Basic object", "Battle", "Beiderstädtischen Amt", "Boarding school", "Body of water", "Bonne ville de l'Empire français", "Border", "Botanical garden", "Building", and "Burschenschaft".

At the bottom right of the interface, there is a "Language for query results:" dropdown menu set to "English (en)".

FactGrid Queries in QGIS (here: Buildings in Koblenz)

id	itemLabel	layerLabel
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q949314	Koblenz, Altengraben 13a	Real estate
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q949314	Koblenz, Altengraben 13a	architectural heritage monument
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q959287	Koblenz, Altengraben 15	Residential building
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q959287	Koblenz, Altengraben 15	Real estate
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q959287	Koblenz, Altengraben 15	Building
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q949315	Koblenz, Altengraben 17	Real estate
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q949315	Koblenz, Altengraben 17	Building
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q949315	Koblenz, Altengraben 17	architectural heritage monument
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q959288	Koblenz, Altengraben 18	Residential building
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q959288	Koblenz, Altengraben 18	Real estate
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q959288	Koblenz, Altengraben 18	Building
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q959289	Koblenz, Altengraben 20	Residential building
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q959289	Koblenz, Altengraben 20	Real estate
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q959289	Koblenz, Altengraben 20	Building
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q949316	Koblenz, Altengraben 25	Real estate
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q949316	Koblenz, Altengraben 25	Real estate
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q949316	Koblenz, Altengraben 25	Building
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q949316	Koblenz, Altengraben 25	Building
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q949316	Koblenz, Altengraben 25	architectural heritage monument
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q949316	Koblenz, Altengraben 25	architectural heritage monument
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q946970	Koblenz, Altengraben 26	Residential building
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q946970	Koblenz, Altengraben 26	Business address
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q946970	Koblenz, Altengraben 26	Building
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q959290	Koblenz, Altengraben 28	Residential building
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q959290	Koblenz, Altengraben 28	Real estate
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q959290	Koblenz, Altengraben 28	Building

nomisma.org - All coins found in Northamptonshire, ordered chronologically by issue

The screenshot displays the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin interface. The main window shows a SPARQL query for finding coins in Northamptonshire, ordered by issue date. The query is as follows:

```
1 PREFIX crm: <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/>
2 SELECT ?item ?type ?date ?place ?lat ?lon WHERE {
3 ?item nmo:hasFindspot/crm:P7_took_place_at/crm:P89_falls_within ?place ;
4 nmo:hasTypeSeriesItem ?type ;
5 a nmo:NumismaticObject .
6 ?place crm:P89_falls_within+ <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q23115> .
7 ?type nmo:hasEndDate ?date .
8 ?place geo:location ?loc .
9 ?loc geo:lat ?lat ;
10 geo:long ?lon .
11 } ORDER BY ASC(?date)
```

The interface also shows a map of Northamptonshire with various towns labeled, including Hinckley, Nuneaton, Coventry, Rugby, Northampton, Kettering, Wellingborough, Bedford, Milton Keynes, and Bletchley. The map displays numerous coin locations marked with colored diamonds. A legend in the bottom right corner indicates the color coding for the coins based on their issue date:

- unicorn_Northamptonshire
- 101 - 0
- 0 - 20
- 20 - 40
- 40 - 189
- 189 - 323
- 323 - 402
- Esri Standard

The word "date" is written vertically next to the legend items.

Roman Open Data - Gauloise 4 Amphoras

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryhelfer Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen: Roman Open Data --> ?item ?lat ?lon [SPARQL Endpoint] Quick Add RDF Resource Filter Concept Results:

Queryvorlagen: 100 Random Geometries Layer Name: rod_Gauloise4

Valid Query

```
1 PREFIX : <http://www.semanticweb.org/ontologies/2015/1/EPNet-ONTOP_Ontology#>
2 PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
3 PREFIX dcterms: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
4 SELECT ?item ?amphtype ?lat ?lon (count(?item) as ?count)
5 WHERE {
6 ?amph a :Amphora .
7 ?amph :hasAmphoraType ?amphtypeo .
8 ?amphtypeo dcterms:title ?amphtype .
9 FILTER (?amphtype = "Gauloise 4")
10 ?amph :carries ?inscription .
11 ?amph :hasFindingPlace ?findplace .
12 ?findplace :fallsWithin ?mun .
13 ?mun a :Municipality .
14 ?mun dcterms:title ?item .
15 ?mun :hasLatitude ?lat .
16 ?mun :hasLongitude ?lon .
17 } ORDER BY ?item DESC(?count)
```

Gespeicherte Queries: Query laden Queryname: Query speichern

Layer hinzufügen

Language for query results: English (en)

GeoConcepts (2)
ont:Municipality
ont:Place

Squirrel Store - Hadrian's Wall Forts

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryhelfer Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen: Research Squirrel Engineers Triplestore --> ?item ?geo [G] Quick Add RDF Resource

Filter Concept Results:

Queryvorlagen: 10 Random Geometries Layer Name: HWforts

Valid Query

```

1 SELECT ?item ?geo ?name ?latin_name ?typeLabel WHERE {
2   ?item rdf:type hw:Fort .
3   ?item geosparql:hasGeometry ?item_geom .
4   ?item_geom geosparql:asWKT ?geo .
5   ?item hw:name ?name .
6   ?item hw:latin_name ?latin_name .
7   ?item a ?type .
8   ?type rdfs:label ?typeLabel .
9   FILTER NOT EXISTS {
10    FILTER (?typeLabel = "Fort"@en)
11  }
12 }

```

Gespeicherte Queries: Query laden Queryname:

	id	latin_name	name	typeLabel
1	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#19	Bibra (?)	Beckfoot	Cumbrian Coast
2	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#4	Condercum	Benwell	Hadrian's Wall
3	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#33	Fanum Cocidi (?)	Bewcastle	Outpost Fort
4	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#38	Vinovia	Binchester	Support Fort
5	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#12	Banna	Birdoswald	Stanegate
6	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#36	Blatobulgium	Birrens	Outpost Fort
7	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#18	Maia	Bowness-on-So...	Hadrian's Wall
8	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#14	-	Brampton Old ...	Stanegate
9	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#39	Brocavum	Brougham	Support Fort
10	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#16	Aballava	Burgh-by-Sands	Hadrian's Wall
11	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#20	-	Burrow Walls	Cumbrian Coast
12	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#23	Luguvalium	Carlisle	Stanegate
13	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#7	Brocolitia	Carrawburgh	Hadrian's Wall
14	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#11	Magna	Carvoran	Stanegate
15	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#13	Camboglanna	Castlesteads	Hadrian's Wall
16	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#27	Concangis	Chester-le-Street	Support Fort
17	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#8	Cilurnum	Chesters	Hadrian's Wall

GeoConcepts (17)

- Watchtower
- hw:CoastalSite
- hw:Cumbrian_Coast
- hw:Curtain_wall
- hw:Fort

unicorn HWforts

- Cumbrian Coast
- Hadrian's Wall
- Outpost Fort
- Stanegate
- Support Fort

OpenStreetMap H.O.T.

Ogham Store - Ogham Stones with *MAQI* (son of)

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryhelfer Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen:

Filter Concept Results:

Queryvorlagen: Layer Name:

Valid Query

```
1 SELECT DISTINCT ?item ?geo ?itemLabel ?stone ?stoneLabel ?readingLabel WHERE {
2 ?stone oghamonto:shows ogham:OW6.
3 ?stone rdfs:label ?stoneLabel .
4 ?stone a oghamonto:OghamStone_CIIC .
5 ?stone oghamonto:disclosedAt ?item .
6 ?item rdfs:label ?itemLabel .
7 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?geom_obj .
8 ?geom_obj geosparql:asWKT ?geo .
9 ?stone oghamonto:carries ?inscription .
10 ?inscription oghamonto:identifiedAs ?reading .
11 ?reading rdfs:label ?readingLabel .
12 FILTER(regex(?readingLabel, "MAQI"))
13 }
```

Gespeicherte Queries: Query laden Queryname: Query speichern

Language for query results:

GeoConcepts (9)

- Barony
- Barony (oghamonto:Barony)
- County
- County (oghamonto:County)
- Feature (geosparql:Feature)
- Geographic Location ...
- Location
- Ogham Site (oghamonto:OghamSite)
- Pleiades Place (Place)

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspots via Solid Pod

The image shows two overlapping windows from the QGIS SPARQLing Unicorn plugin. The top window, titled "Configure Own RDF Resource", is used for setting up a new RDF resource. It includes fields for "Typ der RDF Resource" (set to "RDF Resource als URI"), "RDF Resource Name" ("Campanian Ignimbrite (SolidPod)"), and "RDF Ressourcen URL" (https://fuzzy-sl.solidweb.org/campanian-ignimbrite-geo/ci_full.ttl). It also has options for authentication (set to "HTTP BASIC") and a "Hinzufügen" button.

The bottom window, titled "SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin", shows the main interface. The "Endpoint auswählen:" dropdown is set to "Campanian Ignimbrite (SolidPod) [File]". The "Queryvorlagen:" dropdown is set to "10 Random Geometries". The "Layer Name:" is "sites". The "Valid Query" field contains the following SPARQL query:

```
1 SELECT ?item ?geo ?label ?ref ?spatialType WHERE {
2 ?item a <http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Site> .
3 ?item rdfs:label ?label .
4 ?item <http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/hasReference> ?ref .
5 ?item <http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/spatialType> ?spatialType .
6 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
7 ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
8 }
```

The "Filter Concept Results:" field is empty. The "GeoConcepts (4)" panel shows a tree view with "Entity", "Place", and "Site [71] [71]". The "Site" category is expanded, showing a list of 71 sites, including:

- Acerra Sink (cisite_1)
- Acqua Fidia (cisite_2)
- Balta Alba (Romania) (cisite_57)
- Batajnica (cisite_104)
- Bratul Borcea (Romania) (cisite_56)
- Capezzano (cisite_3)
- Casola (cisite_4)
- Castelcivita Cave (cisite_5)
- Copcecchia (cisite_6)
- Crvena Stijena (Montenegro) (cisite_51)
- Cuma (cisite_7)
- Dobrogea (Romania) (cisite_53)
- Dunaszekcsó (cisite_103)
- Franchthi Cave (Greece) (cisite_45)
- Golema Pesht Cave near Zdunje ...
- Gulf of Naples (cisite_8)

The bottom of the window has buttons for "Gespeicherte Queries:", "Query laden", "Queryname:", "Query speichern", and "Layer hinzufügen". The "Language for query results:" is set to "English (en)".

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspots via Solid Pod

unicorn_sites — Objekte gesamt:104, gefiltert: 104, gewählt: 0

	id	label	ref	spatialType
1	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_1	Acerra Sink	Scandone et al., 1991	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Sink
2	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_2	Acqua Fidia	Rosi et al., 1999	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
3	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_57	Balta Alba (Romania)	Pötter et al., 2021	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
4	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_104	Batajnica	Obreht, I. et al. (2017), Fig. 1	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
5	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_104	Batajnica	Buggle, B. et al. (2013)	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
6	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_104	Batajnica	Buggle, B. et al. (2014)	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
7	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_56	Bratul Borcea (Romania)	Pötter et al., 2021	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
8	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_3	Capeziano	Rosi et al., 1999	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/InhabitedPlace
9	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_4	Casola	Rosi et al., 1999	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/InhabitedPlace
10	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_5	Castelcivita Cave	Fedele et al., 2008	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Cave
11	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_5	Castelcivita Cave	Giaccio et al., 2008	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Cave
12	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_6	Copcechia	Rosi et al., 1999	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
13	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_51	Crvena Stijena (Montenegro)	Morley & Woodward, 2011	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Cave
14	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_51	Crvena Stijena (Montenegro)	Morley & Woodward, 2011	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/ArchaeologicalSite
15	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_7	Cuma	Pappalardo et al., 1999	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
16	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_53	Dobrogea (Romania)	Fitzsimmons et al., 2014	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Plateau
17	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_53	Dobrogea (Romania)	Fitzsimmons et al., 2013	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Plateau
18	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_103	Dunazekcsó	Obreht, I. et al. (2017), Fig. 1	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
19	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_103	Dunazekcsó	Újvári, G. Et al. (2016)	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
20	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_45	Franchthi Cave (Greece)	Fedele et al., 2003	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Cave
21	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_45	Franchthi Cave (Greece)	Fedele et al., 2003	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/ArchaeologicalSite
22	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_50	Golema Pesht Cave near Zdu...	Lowe et al., 2012	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Cave
23	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_50	Golema Pesht Cave near Zdu...	Lowe et al., 2012	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/ArchaeologicalSite
24	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_8	Gulf of Naples	Arienzo et al., 2009	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Bight
25	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_65	Haua-Feah (Libya)	Lowe et al., 2012	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Cave
26	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_65	Haua-Feah (Libya)	Lowe et al., 2012	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/ArchaeologicalSite
27	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_61	Kisiljevo (Serbia)	Baykal et al., 2018	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
28	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_46	Klissoura (Greece)	Lowe et al., 2012	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
29	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_60	Kostenki (Russia)	Fedele et al., 2003	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/InhabitedPlace
30	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_59	Kostenki-Borshevo (Russia)	Fedele et al., 2008	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/ArchaeologicalSite

Alle Objekte anzeigen

Transformation from CSV / GeoJSON into RDF (e.g. GeoSPARQL)

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot CSV to RDF

id	label	desc	literature	wkt	certainty	certaintyinfo
1	Acerra Sink	CI findspot related from literature	Scandone et al., 1991	POINT(14.3624 40.9489)	fs:medium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
2	Acqua Fidia	CI findspot related from literature	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.6983 40.9285)	fs:medium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
3	Capezzano	CI findspot related from literature	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.7680 40.7119)	fs:medium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
4	Casola	CI findspot related from literature	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.5259 40.6993)	fs:medium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
5	Castelvita Cave	CI findspot related from literature	Fedele et al., 2008;Giaccio et al., 2008	POINT(15.2092 40.4956)	fs:high	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
6	Copecchia	CI findspot related from literature	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.7662 40.7198)	fs:medium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
7	Cuma	CI findspot related from literature	Pappalardo et al., 1999	POINT(14.0560 40.8381)	fs:medium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
8	Gulf of Naples	CI findspot related from literature	Arienzo et al., 2009	POINT(14.2559 40.7192)	fs:medium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
9	Lago Patria (Naples)	CI findspot related from literature	Civetta et al., 1997;Scandone et al., 1991	POINT(14.0366 40.9260)	fs:medium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
10	Marina di Cassano (Naples)	CI findspot related from literature	Civetta et al., 1997	POINT(14.3998 40.6385)	fs:medium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
11	Massaquano (Naples)	CI findspot related from literature	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.4476 40.6619)	fs:medium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
12	Monte Echia (Naples)	CI findspot related from literature	Pappalardo et al., 1999	POINT(14.0560 40.8381)	fs:medium	scientific paper
13	Lago Grande di Monticchio	CI findspot related from literature	Narcisi, 1996	POINT(14.0560 40.8381)	fs:medium	scientific paper
14	Monticchio (Bagni)	CI findspot related from literature	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.0560 40.8381)	fs:medium	scientific paper
15	Monticchio Lakes	CI findspot related from literature	Brauer et al., 1999	POINT(14.0560 40.8381)	fs:medium	scientific paper
16	Murge Plateau	CI findspot related from literature	Giaccio et al., 2008	POINT(14.0560 40.8381)	fs:medium	scientific paper

Hinzuzufügende Elemente wählen | cifindspots_part_full

C:\git\workshop-osf24-mainz\src\cifindspots_part_full.csv

Suche...

Element	Beschreibung
Point (71)	

Alle wählen Alle abwählen

Optionen

Layer zu einer Gruppe hinzufügen

System und interne Tabellen anzeigen

Leere Vektorlayer anzeigen

Layer hinzufügen Abbrechen

QGIS3

Dieser Layer scheint keine Projektionsangaben zu besitzen. Die Projektion dieses Layers wird auf die des Projektes voreingestellt. Sie können es jedoch unten durch auswählen einer anderen Projektion überschreiben.

Vordefiniertes KBS

Filter

Kürzlich benutzte Koordinatenbezugssysteme

Koordinatensystem	AutoritätsID
WGS 84 / Pseudo-Mercator	EPSG:3857
WGS 84	EPSG:4326

Vordefinierte Koordinatenreferenzsystem Veraltete KBS verbergen

Koordinatenbezugssystem	AutoritätsID
Voirlo 1879 (Paris)	EPSG:4821
Wake Island 1952	EPSG:4733
Wallis (MOP 1976) geographiq...	IGNF:WALL76G
Wallis (MOP 1978) geographiq...	IGNF:WALL78G
WGS 66	EPSG:4760
WGS 72	EPSG:4322
WGS 72BE	EPSG:4324
WGS 84	EPSG:4326

WGS 84

Eigenschaften

- Geographisch (verwendet Längen- und Breitengrad für Koordinaten)
- Dynamisch (hängt von einem Datum ab, das nicht plattenfixiert ist)
- Überirdischer Körper: Earth
- Basierend auf World Geodetic

OK Abbrechen Hilfe

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot CSV to RDF

cfindspots_part_full — Objekte gesamt:71, gefiltert: 71, gewählt: 0

id	label	desc	literature	wkt	certainty	certaintyinfo	relatedto	relatedtohow	source	sourcetype	spatialtype	methodtype	agent	methoddesc
1	Acerra Sink	CI findspot rela...	Scandone et al., ...	POINT(14.3624 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	https://sws.geo...	fspartyMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslSink	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
2	Acqua Fidia	CI findspot rela...	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.6983 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	https://www.op...	fslspatialClose...	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslUnknownCat...	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
3	Capezzano	CI findspot rela...	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.7680 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslInhabitedPlace	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
4	Casola	CI findspot rela...	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.5259 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	https://www.op...	fslspatialClose...	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslInhabitedPlace	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
5	Castelcivita Cave	CI findspot rela...	Fedele et al., 20...	POINT(15.2092 ...	fslhigh	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslCave	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
6	Copcechia	CI findspot rela...	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.7662 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslUnknownCat...	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
7	Cuma	CI findspot rela...	Pappalardo et a...	POINT(14.0560 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslUnknownCat...	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
8	Gulf of Naples	CI findspot rela...	Aienzo et al., 2...	POINT(14.2559 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	https://sws.geo...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslBight	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
9	Lago Patria (Na...	CI findspot rela...	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.0366 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	https://sws.geo...	fslspatialClose...	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslInhabitedPlace	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
10	Marina di Cassa...	CI findspot rela...	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.3998 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://sws.geo...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslBight	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
11	Massaquano (N...	CI findspot rela...	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.4476 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslInhabitedPlace	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
12	Monte Echia (N...	CI findspot rela...	Pappalardo et a...	POINT(14.2479 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslMountain	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
13	Lago Grande di...	CI findspot rela...	Narcisi, 1996	POINT(15.6057 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	https://sws.geo...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslLake	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
14	Monticchio (Ba...	CI findspot rela...	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(15.5699 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslInhabitedPlace	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
15	Monticchio Lakes	CI findspot rela...	Brauer et al., 20...	POINT(15.6098...	fslhigh	findspot menti...	https://www.op...	fslspatialClose...	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslLake	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
16	Murge Plateau	CI findspot rela...	Giaccio et al., 2...	POINT(16.2833 ...	fslow	findspot menti...	https://sws.geo...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslPlateau	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
17	Naples	CI findspot rela...	Civetta et al., 1996	POINT(14.2080 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslInhabitedPlace	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
18	Pacognano	CI findspot rela...	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.4347 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	https://www.op...	fslspatialClose...	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslInhabitedPlace	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
19	Paglicci Cave	CI findspot rela...	Giaccio et al., 2...	POINT(15.6150 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslCave/fslArch...	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
20	Pellezzano	CI findspot rela...	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.7546 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslInhabitedPlace	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
21	Penta	CI findspot rela...	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.7979 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslInhabitedPlace	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
22	Phlegraean Fields	CI findspot rela...	Orsi et al., 1996...	POINT(14.1402 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslSupervolcano	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
23	Ponti Rossi (Na...	CI findspot rela...	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.2594 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	https://sws.geo...	fspartyMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslUnknownCat...	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
24	Pozzuoli Bay	CI findspot rela...	Civetta et al., 1996	POINT(14.0890 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	https://sws.geo...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslBight	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
25	Pucara	CI findspot rela...	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.6459 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://openstre...	fslspatialClose...	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslUnknownCat...	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
26	Punta Marmolite	CI findspot rela...	Pappalardo et a...	POINT(14.1489 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	fslspatialClose...	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslUnknownCat...	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
27	Sant' Agata dei ...	CI findspot rela...	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.3733 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslInhabitedPlace	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
28	Sant' Angelo a ...	CI findspot rela...	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.7402 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslInhabitedPlace	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
29	San Marco	CI findspot rela...	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.3381 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslInhabitedPlace	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
30	San Nicola La S...	CI findspot rela...	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.3313 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslInhabitedPlace	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot CSV to RDF


```
suni:c434e049-c2ab-4308-8d6b-b3247b5ffba0 a suni:d1f06db3-dd8c-4b96-a360-f28909f76c65 ;
suni:agent <http://orcid.org/0009-0008-2877-3204> ;
suni:certainty "fsl:medium"^^xsd:string ;
suni:certaintyinfo "Fitzsimmons et al. (2014), p.76: "In this paper we investigate [...] the site of Urluia Quarry on the Dobrogea loess plateau [...], some 15 km south of the Danube River. The site immediately overlies the Quaternary-uplifted Cretaceous-Tertiary-age limestone basement rocks (Munteanu et al., 2008), which were the target of earlier quarrying activities."; Pötter et al. (2021), p.5: "The Urluia (URL) LPS is located in an abandoned limestone quarry on the limestone plateau of the Dobrogea (Fitzsimmons et al., 2013; Fitzsimmons and Hambach, 2014; Obreht et al., 2017).""^^xsd:string ;
suni:desc "CI findspot related from literature"^^xsd:string ;
suni:label "Urluia (Romania)"^^xsd:string ;
suni:literature "Fitzsimmons et al., 2014;Fitzsimmons et al., 2013;Obreht et al., 2017;Pötter et al., 2021"^^xsd:string ;
suni:methoddesc "set a representative point based on scientific papers using Google Maps"^^xsd:string ;
suni:methodtype "fsl:Georeferencing"^^xsd:string ;
suni:relatedto <http://sws.geonames.org/664132;http://openstreetmap.org/way/84975654> ;
suni:relatedtohow "skos:closeMatch"^^xsd:string ;
suni:source "fsl:PaperDesc"^^xsd:string ;
suni:sourcetype "fsl:Paper"^^xsd:string ;
suni:spatialtype "fsl:InhabitedPlace"^^xsd:string ;
suni:wkt "POINT(27.9021 44.0947)"^^xsd:string ;
geo:hasGeometry suni:c434e049-c2ab-4308-8d6b-b3247b5ffba0_geom .
```

```
suni:c434e049-c2ab-4308-8d6b-b3247b5ffba0_geom a geo:Point ;
geo:asWKT "Point (27.902100000000000079 44.0947000000000000312)"^^geo:wktLiteral .
```

European River Network GeoJSON to RDF

NAME	Shape_Leng
Danube	2770357,36328
Douro	816245,218931
Ebro	826990,879516
Elbe	1087288,26667
Guadalquivir	599758,347758
Guadiana	1063055,37701
Loire	944755,381131
Nemunas	689209,621531
Odra	823753,80297
Rhine	1159962,39349
Rhone	910617,937531
Sava	625964,046091
Seine	673648,436798

European River Network GeoJSON to RDF

```
suni:5eb80411-ee91-47ef-a3a2-89c6440709b5 a suni:7babd7e6-5fc0-457f-8e46-d37bcb9c9d7b ;
suni:NAME "Rhine"^^xsd:string ;
suni:Shape_Leng 1.159962e+06 ;
geo:hasGeometry suni:5eb80411-ee91-47ef-a3a2-89c6440709b5_geom .
```

```
suni:5eb80411-ee91-47ef-a3a2-89c6440709b5_geom a geo:MultiLineString ;
geo:asWKT "MultiLineString ((5.94425373459836237 51.94878151289067603, 5.95763502500831166 51.92072893309910597, 5.99252667260233185 51.8943079853457121,
6.0197039927329099 51.87012905448126787, 6.02354236358268835 51.86903159930916729, 6.03614239689617094 51.86578946616741348, 6.04172145893227608
51.86470845172616606, 6.04784263528278299 51.86363235561832141, 6.0519818996624748 51.86236926894400767, 6.06206365752319343 51.85696996339164855,
6.06494240075981139 51.85552874023783687, 6.07239335244463962 51.85561952215852699, 6.07286273716284164 51.85535107166987245, 6.07754296641921421
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6.59703544566211697 51.58498682846255434 6.5970358692740998 51.57850658718345471 6.59883595959811323 51.57544683530344543 6.60117592154422983
```


RDF HTML-Documentation

Roman Province Borders to HTML

	id	label
1	1	Reatia-Noricum
2	2	Raetia-Noricum
3	3	Italia
4	4	Creta et Cyrene
5	5	Baetica-Tarraconensis
6	6	Mauretania Tingetana
7	7	Lusitania-Baetica
8	8	Lusitania-Tarraconensis
9	9	Tarraconensis-Gallia Narbonensis
10	10	Creta et Cyrene-Africa Proconsularis
11	11	Mauretania Tingetana
12	12	Africa Proconsularis-Mauretania Caesarensis
13	13	Britannia
14	14	Alpes Poeniae-Gallia Belgica
15	15	Arabia
16	16	Aegyptus-Creta et Cyrene
17	17	Aegyptus-Creta et Cyrene
18	18	Arabia
19	19	Bytinia et Pontus-Asia
20	20	Asia-Lycia
21	21	Noricum-Barbaricum
22	22	Dalmatia-Moesia
23	23	Macadonia-Moesia
24	24	Macedonia-Achaia
25	25	Thracia-Moesia
26	26	Thracia-Macedonia

Create HTML Documentation from RDF

HTML result (Start Page)

Index page for <http://www.github.com/sparqlunicorn#>

http://www.github.com/sparqlunicorn#suni_dataset powered by Static GeoPubby generated using the [SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin OntDoc Script 0.17](#)

Search: Download Options: Format: Turtle (TTL)

This page shows information about linked data resources in HTML. Choose the classtree navigation or search to browse the data

Download VOWL File Download Mini VOWL File

Show 10 entries

Class	Number of Instances	Instance Example
871b27c4-d62d-4a98-8578-cacc42df70d2 (suni:871b27c4-d62d-4a98-8578-cacc42df70d2) [78]	4	Gallia Belgica-Germania Inferior (suni:011bac95-d80d-412b-b734-bd1a3a5bdc)

- PrimeMeridian (geocrs:PrimeMeridian) [1]
- SpatialObject (gsp:SpatialObject)
- Feature (gsp:Feature)
 - 871b27c4-d62d-4a98-8578-cacc42df70d2 (suni:871b27c4-d62d-4a98-8578-cacc42df70d2)
 - Aegyptus-Creta et Cyrene (suni:41bfa2a0-8582-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Aegyptus-Creta et Cyrene (suni:975c1740-2e22-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Africa Proconsularis-Mauretania Caesarensis (suni:b99c72-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Alpes Cottiae-Alpes Graiae et Poen. (suni:b99c72-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Alpes Poeniae-Gallia Belgica (suni:b82091f-5d0-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Alpes Poeniae-Raetia (suni:af4089c9-4bb9-41b1-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Alpes marines-Alpes (suni:6d0a1abd-7ed7-433c-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Arabia (suni:180cba4b-91bf-4ccc-bb49-b6d11405-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Arabia (suni:fd506cfe-26d2-48fd-b665-65570581-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Asia-Lycia (suni:6b099876-5f96-4111-b3bc-0956-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Baetica-Tarraconensis (suni:ecd4a284-5f39-45a1-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Britannia (suni:5853ef83-2d77-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Bytynia et Pontus-Asia (suni:e6a399fd-2206-4301-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Bytynia et Pontus-Cappadocia (suni:22d97328-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Cappadocia-Armenia (suni:c7434610-6197-4a21-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Cilicia-Cappadocia (suni:d35f3c41-2542-4b08-9b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Creta et Cyrene (suni:71947e99-a3ca-4062-9d91-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Creta et Cyrene-Africa Proconsularis (suni:be214-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Dacia-Barbaricum (suni:38692482-c381-46fa-aff1-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Dalmatia-Moesia (suni:5921f34c-8fd1-4667-8674-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Dalmatia-Pannonia (suni:6232bfb3-840e-47ef-b1b1-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Galatia-Bytynia et Pontus (suni:44a208bf-d85a-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Galatia-Cappadocia (suni:31df4a47-7635-45ce-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Galatia-Cappadocia (suni:92b5934e-6d7b-4841-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Galatia-Cappadocia (suni:fd692685-b083-47ae-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Galatia-Galicia (suni:477fbc08-0db6-4992-ba6c-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Gallia Aquitania-Gallia Lugdunensis (suni:08c1b1-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Gallia Aquitania-Gallia Lugdunensis (suni:1e9db1-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Gallia Aquitania-Gallia Lugdunensis (suni:a506b1-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Gallia Belgica-Gallia Narbonensis (suni:ec41e81-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Gallia Belgica-Germania Inferior (suni:011bac95-d80d-412b-b734-bd1a3a5bdc)
 - Gallia Belgica-Germania Inferior (suni:973c6a5a-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Gallia Belgica-Raetia (suni:b8abd85-3eb7-459a-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Gallia Lugdunensis-Alpes (suni:24917928-8b16-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Gallia Lugdunensis-Gallia Belgica (suni:2a56b51-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Gallia Lugdunensis-Gallia Belgica (suni:c28f9ba-4b60-9ebd-5057c)
 - Gallia Lugdunensis-Gallia Narbonensis (suni:251-4b60-9ebd-5057c)

HTML result (Spatial Instances Collection)

871b27c4-d62d-4a98-8578-cacc42df70d2 Instances Collection

http://www.github.com/sparqlunicorn#871b27c4-d62d-4a98-8578-cacc42df70d2_collection powered by Static GeoPubby generated using the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin OntDoc Script 0.17

Search: Go Download Options: Format: Turtle (TTL) Download Query

GeoClasses: X

Search:

- AxisDirection (geocrs:AxisDirection) [2]
- CoordinateSystemAxis (geocrs:CoordinateSystemAxis) [2]
- Ellipsoid (geocrs:Ellipsoid) [1]
- EllipsoidalCoordinateSystem (geocrs:EllipsoidalCoordinateSystem) [1]
- Entity (prov:Entity) [1]
- GeodeticReferenceFrame (geocrs:GeodeticReferenceFrame) [1]
- GeographicCRS (geocrs:GeographicCRS) [1]
- PlanarCoordinateSystem (geocrs:PlanarCoordinateSystem) [1]
- PrimeMeridian (geocrs:PrimeMeridian) [1]
- SpatialObject (gsp:SpatialObject)
- SpatialReferenceSystem (geocrs:SpatialReferenceSystem) [1]
- Unit (om:Unit) [1]
- Collection (skos:Collection) [1]
- SpatialObjectCollection (gsp:SpatialObjectCollection)
- FeatureCollection (gsp:FeatureCollection) [1]
- 871b27c4-d62d-4a98-8578-cacc42df70d2 Instances Co**
- GeometryCollection (gsp:GeometryCollection) [1]
- LineString Instances Collection (suni:LineString_collecti

Property	Value
type (rdf:type)	FeatureCollection (gsp:FeatureCollection)
label (rdfs:label)	871b27c4-d62d-4a98-8578-cacc42df70d2 Instances Collection (rdf:langString) (iso6391:en)
member (rdfs:member)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">78 valuesAegyptus-Creta et Cyrene (suni:41bfa2a0-8582-4ef0-a98e-a54965a9547c)Aegyptus-Creta et Cyrene (suni:975c1740-2a22-4c50-a127-1fe800d6005)Africa Proconsularis-Mauretania Caesarensis (suni:7f8d220a-10aa-46df-a00f-b338677d3dcf)Alpes Cotiae-Alpes Graiae et Poen. (suni:b69c72de-95ad-4e8c-96b7-e89cd2b99701)Alpes Poeninae-Gallia Belgica (suni:b8f2091f-5d01-4de1-9041-bcd6b608ed03)Alpes Poeninae-Raetia (suni:af4089c9-4bb9-41b8-b856-5d54d48f7f11)Alpes marines-Alpes (suni:6d0a1abd-7ed7-433d-a2b8-894dfee284cc)Arabia (suni:f80cba4b-91bf-4ccc-bb49-b6d114054d94)Arabia (suni:fd50cfe-26d2-48fd-b665-6557d5059942)Asia-Lycia (suni:6d099076-5f96-4111-b3bc-095644dc5b8c)Baetica-Tarconensis (suni:ecd4a284-5f39-45a6-bceb-6d28d20f9135)Britannia (suni:5853ef83-2d77-4b60-9ebd-5057c11c4422)Bytynia et Pontus-Asia (suni:e6a399fd-2206-430d-95b3-ae6566172012)Bytynia et Pontus-Cappadocia (suni:22d97328-4f03-4f83-a87b-ed1cf9a85af0)Cappadocia-Armenia (suni:c7434610-6197-4a2e-b9d6-ad0deb13b27a)Cilicia-Cappadocia (suni:d35f3c41-2542-4b08-9a81-b737af751f8e)Creta et Cyrene (suni:71947e99-a3ca-40b2-9d96-714290ccea65)Creta et Cyrene-Africa Proconsularis (suni:be2141f9-2eac-4360-91f9-4008d0dc6e59)

HTML result (Britannia)

Britannia

<http://www.github.com/sparqlunicorn#5853ef83-2d77-4b60-9ebd-5057c11c4422> powered by Static GeoPubby generated using the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin OntDoc Script 0.17

Search: Go Download Options: Format: Turtle (TTL) Download Query

Property	Value
hasGeometry (gsp:hasGeometry)	5853ef83-2d77-4b60-9ebd-5057c11c4422_geom (suni:5853ef83-2d77-4b60-9ebd-5057c11c4422_geom)
type (rdf:type)	871b27c4-d62d-4a98-8578-cacc42df70d2 (suni:871b27c4-d62d-4a98-8578-cacc42df70d2)
label (rdfs:label)	Britannia (xmls:string)
is member (rdfs:member) of	871b27c4-d62d-4a98-8578-cacc42df70d2_Instances Collection (suni:871b27c4-d62d-4a98-8578-cacc42df70d2_collection)

Metadata

Property	Value
inDataset (void:inDataset)	suni_dataset (suni:suni_dataset) [796 geocrs:longitude]

This work is released under

Finis!
Thx :-)

Questions?

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Tobias Arera-Rütenik, tobias.arera-ruetenik@uni-bamberg.de, ORCID: 0000-0002-4703-9573

